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About The Tribal Research & Cultural Institute & “Tui”- The Journal

The Tribal Research & Cultural Institute was established in 1970 under the Tribal Welfare Department to locate, revive and register folk culture— literature, music, dance, cuisine, attire, ornaments— of the state of Tripura. Its main objectives were to carry out research on the development of language and culture, socio-economic condition of the ethnic communities, collection of historical elements and evaluation studies. Organizing state and national seminars, producing films, establishing social science library and a state Tribal Museum have a part of its broad schema.

“Tui: A Journal of Tribal Life & Culture” was established in 1993 to continue with and aid the objectives of the Department. Its last volume, XXI No.02, was published in March 2018. TUI is a peer-reviewed, bi-annual journal.

Editor's Note

Established under the aegis of The Tribal Research & Cultural Institute, Government of Tripura, “TUI –a journal on Tribal Life and culture” has come a long way in its journey of ‘locating, reviving and registering folk culture— literature, music, dance, cuisine, attire, ornaments’ from its commencement in 1993.

The current volume of “TUI” takes a stride beyond the state of Tripura and connects its folk culture to myriad other folk cultures that abound our nation. The papers attempt at studying cultures that were pushed to the margins for a considerably long-time starting colonialism. This not only resulted in submergence of communities politically— thereby creating subalterns— but also culturally, an attempt at eradicating different ways of life altogether. This volume reflects on the long-submerged epistemologies of indigenous critical approaches— both postcolonial and post-occidental— that leads to a ‘decolonial view of humanity’ giving rise to recognition of differences and thereby paving the way for a new humanism.

The volume broadly covers Postcolonial studies focusing on the following sub-themes: Non-western epistemology, Folklore/Folk Stories as parallel world views, Nature in folk literature, Indigenous aesthetics, Local as Global in indigenous literature, Vicissitudes of documenting the local in a Global (English) Language.

— **Dr. Pronami Bhattacharyya**

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The Portrayal of Nature and Morality in select Folktales of the Garos

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Abstract

The paper aims at determining how the children's folktales, which have morality as well as the awe-inspiring natural phenomenon, flora and fauna of Garo hills, balance the nature and environment through the texts. It also illustrates how these stories are portrayed in the concept of nature in different short stories in the A·chik Golporang Bak I, II and III (Garo folktales/folklore) and Folktale of the Garos published by Dhoronsing K Sangma in 1984 and Dewangsing Rongmuthu in 1960 respectively. This article examines 10 children's stories which are focused on the perception of nature and environment. The methodology for this study is content analysis that includes methods of qualitative data collection and analysis. As result of the content analysis, 10 folktales' subjects are identified as having templates of nature-human interaction, natural life and elements of nature. These stories focus on the interaction of nature and human beings as well as among the different species of the animal kingdom. The examined folktales present nature in different ways. They have descriptions of nature, while few of them describe a day in nature having moral values. One of the children's stories, in the folktale of the Garos, "The Tiger and the Pangolin", two species of wildlife, found in the Garo Hills, illustrate the interaction between these two animals and portrays the natural instincts through the morality in the narrative. These folktales of the Garos have been examined to expose their portrayal of nature and natural phenomenon having moral values within them to improve children's behavior and their outlook of life. The metaethics started by G.E. Moore (1903) in his book *Principia Ethica* and moral theory given by Immanuel Kant (1724-1804) in his book; *Groundwork of the metaphysics of morals* (1785) has been applied to the description of the folktales of the Garos.

Keywords: Nature, environmental education, child stories, pictures, qualitative research, content analysis

Introduction

Folktales are stories that have been passed down orally from one generation to the next. Such tales are being gathered and recorded in the modern era, as the oral storytelling tradition gives way to e-books in smart phones and computers, books and television. Folktales occasionally attempt to explain the world in which we live. They occasionally recount actual people, places and occasions, as in the case of the Dombe Wari story as found in Sangma (1988, pp. 73-76) and Rongmuthu (2008, pp. 4-7). Mermaids/Mermen, nature and gods frequently coexist peacefully with regular people in folklore and myth. Favorite character types may also be at the center of folktales. A particular character or group of characters may occasionally capture our attention and inspire dozens of stories to be told about them such as the te'tengs 'Imps', buga rani 'mermaid', buga raja 'mermen' etc. These mythical figures come in a wide variety.

Folk refers to the common people or the general masses. People of all castes, creeds, and religions are included in the term "common people." The term "Folk" is used to describe a group of people who share the same customs and traditions, according to folk-culturists. In addition, it might be a reference to communal living, language and religious sharing, etc. (Sarmah, 1997). As opposed to the folk society, the term "folk" in literature refers to particularly constrained concepts. According to Sarmah (1999), "Folk normally refer to the working class of villages and towns living under the canopy of traditions and customs". They essentially lack access to formal education. Folktales deal with the working class from this perspective. Folk literature includes a lot of folktales and it exists as evidence. Tales, myths, legends, proverbs, poetry, jokes, and other oral traditions are all included in folklore. They consist of tangible cultural practices like the group's customary architectural designs. Customary lore, acting on behalf of folk beliefs, and the forms and rituals

of holidays like Christmas, weddings, folk dances, and initiation ceremonies are all included in folklore. Each of them is regarded as a folklore artifact or a traditional cultural manifestation, either separately or together. Folklore includes the transfer of these artifacts from one place or generation to the next, which is just as important as the form (Dundes, 1965).

Metaethics or Analytic Ethics

Metaethics, as expressed by Kant (1785), is also known as analytic ethics, is the name of the second component of the philosophical approach to the study of ethics. His definition of analytic ethics is Kant (1785) “Act only according to that maxim by which you can at the same time will that it should become a universal law.” This strategy is analytical in two respects, as opposed to being descriptive or prescriptive. According to Krasemann and Thiroux (2011), Metaethicists examine ethical language first (e.g., what we mean when we use the word ‘good’). Second, they examine the intellectual bases for ethical theories, or the arguments put out by diverse ethicists. Metaethicists do not make recommendations or deal directly with normative structures. Instead, they “go beyond” (a crucial meaning of the Greek prefix meta-), addressing normative ethical systems solely inferentially by putting more of an emphasis on language, logical frameworks, and reasoning than on substance.

It should be mentioned that, although being employed by all ethicists to some extent, metaethics has largely taken over as the focus of contemporary ethical philosophers. This might be partly explained by how challenging it is to create an ethical code that can be applied to all, or even most, people. Finding an ethical framework to guide the behaviors of all people is a challenging, if not impossible, undertaking in today’s increasingly complex and heterogeneous globe, cultures, and lifestyles. These philosophers like Kant (1785) and Moore (1903) believe that rather than attempting to develop ethical frameworks that will aid in human beings living together more meaningfully and ethically, it would be better to focus on language and

logic like other specialists have done. Philosophers consider common moral adages or truisms, conceptual studies of moral ideas, the structure of everyday language, and the nature of moral phenomenology. A unified theory regarding the state of morality is the aim or purpose of this research. In other words, philosophers are attempting to methodically define and assemble the reality that requires justification.

According to Michael Gill (Gill 2009), the paradigmatic approach to metaethics involves a two-stage process. This process' initial step entails "collecting examples of moral ideas and terms in common language and thought...canvassing common sense, moral judgments, linguistic intuitions, and platitudes" (p. 217). Here, philosophers almost inevitably reach the axiom that moral discourse in everyday life is devoted to moral absolutism, that morality is understood by the average person to be the exchange of mind-independent moral facts, and that if two people disagree on a moral matter, at least one of them must be mistaken. Philosophers then proceed to the second stage of the process, which entails trying to defend a specific, systematic theory based on the data gathered in the first stage, typically with a conceptual characterization of morality as having a particular shape or structure. This second stage of the analysis will support customary moral behavior, according to some philosophers. In other words, some philosophers contend that morality is actually objective and absolute in nature, just as people generally believe. On the other hand, some philosophers contend that morality is not objective and absolute and that common moral practice is flawed. For the time being, it's crucial to keep in mind that philosophers generally concur at the first stage that everyday moral behavior is committed to objectivism, regardless of what theory emerges from this two-stage process (whether it's a form of realism, relativism, expressivism, etc.).

Moral Theory

According to the "Webster New World Dictionary of American Language," morality has to do with the ability to discern between acceptable citizen behavior

that is right and wrong. According to Bentham, morality is an art that seeks to maximize happiness; it can be observed by achieving a happy and joyful existence for everyone. (Hazlitt, 2003, p. 119) A morality is the exchange of small goodness for large goodness (Hazlitt, 2003, p. 111). According to William James Earle, the word “moral” (/’mɔrəl/ in modern English) comes from the Greek word “Ethos,” which denotes behavior, character, personal disposition, and tendency. The words moral and morality come from the Latin word *mores*, which also means custom, manner, and character (Earle, 1992, p. 178) following the accepted standards of behavior in society. Morals are also based on a conscience-based sense of right and wrong: moral courage, moral law. A moral victory or a moral defeat is moral support that has the effects of (victory or defeat) but not the appearance of it. Sternberg (1994) writes “Morality refers to concern with what is good or right in people’s relationships with one another” (p. 938).

It is important to be precise when defining what is good (or bad) and what is right (or wrong), as these concepts can be evaluated according to criteria like efficiency or level of care when making decisions. Being precise in your definition of what is good or bad and what is right or wrong is a key to understanding morality. The statement “morality contains beliefs about the nature of human beings, beliefs about ideals, about what is good or desirable or worthy of pursuit for its own sake, rules laying down what ought to be done, and motives that incline us to choose the right or the wrong” refers to beliefs about what is good or desirable or worthy of pursuit. A morality consists of: (1) beliefs about the nature of man, (2) beliefs about ideals, about what is right or desirable or worthwhile of pursuit for its own sake, (3) rules outlining what should be done, and (4) motivations that lead us to take the right or wrong course. When we are young, we are taught to be selfless and to not tell lies (Edwards, 1972, p. 150).

The Discussion on the Portrayal of Nature and Morality in select Folktales of Garo

The moral importance of youth is the main topic of this paper. Through the

moral lessons found in Garo folktales, it addresses the meaning of life. It makes use of the morality displayed by the main characters in the folktales in everyday life. Moral refers to accepted social norms of behavior and right behavior as well as an individual's behavior in relation to the morals of civilization. Moral can refer to or be concerned with the standards of proper behavior or the difference between right and wrong; ethical: moral principles stating or delivering truths or advice regarding proper conduct (Sternberg 1994, p. 938).

Moral obligations are those that are based on the fundamental rules of right conduct rather than on laws, regulations, or customs. A moral being is one who is capable of abiding by the moral laws. A moral man is one who upholds the standards of moral behavior as opposed to acting immorally. It could be a fable, story, experience, etc. that contains a moral lesson or practical lesson. Folktales are used as primary source in this paper.

Moral values can be transmitted in a variety of ways through folktales. Folktales, according to Lindahl (2004), are narratives that are passed down from one generation to the next. They are an invaluable source of creative content that preserves a particular culture's oral tradition. Some folktales combine elements of reality and fantasy. Everywhere in the world, folktales function in the same way: by verbally passing down a collective tradition. Its stories, characters, language, and depiction of life are how it transmits. Folktales often have kid-friendly, legendary, tall tale, or humorous themes.

Additionally, folktales may offer methods for increasing people's awareness of various sociocultural norms and various notions of politeness in particular social contexts. Folktales, as literature, demonstrate the importance of culture in language learning for the achievement of meaningful communication and the understanding of a particular language, according to Lindahl (2004). All of this is based on the understanding that when reading unfamiliar discourse, a learner of a foreign language may make incorrect assumptions that are caused by cultural misunderstanding.

Folktales from the Garo people have long been a part of their culture.

Hunter-gatherers, farmers, small-band societies, and theocracies with complex hierarchies are all part of the native Garo culture. According to Wolfram (2007), one needs to have sufficient linguistic, rhetorical, and cultural knowledge to understand folktales. It is because folktales, which are based on oral tradition, are a literary genre with a heavy emphasis on dialogue. Understanding those dialogues requires knowledge of linguistic principles typically categorized as pragmatic, and particularly sociopragmatic. Based on the explanations given above, this paper discusses the moral significance of Garo folktales.

The current paper's goal is to conduct a textual analysis of how the notion of nature/environment and morality is expressed in children's folktales from the Garo culture.

Findings in the ten folktales of the Garos portraying Nature and Morality

The findings in the ten folktales of the Garos portraying Nature and Morality has been divided under the sub-terms for better understanding of these Human-Nature interaction, Negative Behaviors towards Nature, Descriptions of Nature, Fauna in nature, Natural Living and the moral story behind them.

A. Human-Nature Interaction

1) Dombe Wari 'Dombe Lake'

The villagers thought that Dome Rani, who was already married to Joreng, was beautiful. There was a merman who, after hearing Joreng boast about his wife to the trees in the forest, was curious and wanted to see Dombe rani for himself. Dombe was the love of Joreng's life, but his pride at having a wife who resembled a goddess would make him unhappy. One of the merman made the decision to go to the village after learning about Dombe and pretended to be a human selling *samgong* or "bangle" to the locals. He finds Dombe and is so overcome by her beauty that he

cannot stop wanting her. He attached a magical *sanggong* ‘bangle’ to Dombé’s wrist that she could not remove. She made several attempts to remove the bangle from her wrist, but she was unsuccessful. The merman then permitted her to wear it while assuring her that he would return for the bangle in the future. Sangma (1988, p. 74) describes this event of the merman giving the enchanted bangle to Dombé as “*adita salni ja·mano Bugarik pante nambegipa sonani sandap ba sanggong (jaksan jorasako) dake Dombema·angni songona re·angaha, ua salo apalgipa sa·rao me·chik jinma mitangtangko damsansu·tokengachim. Bugarik pante ...Ia jaksan jorasa nang·ni ong·jok*” (As soon as Joreng learns of the incident, he is determined to protect her and takes her far away from the river and the merman, where he builds a house on top of a massive tree at the top of the hill. Then, with the aid of sangkni, the “mythical snake,” and other fabled aquatic creatures, a desperate and enraged merman causes a flood and engulfs her). Later, this developed into the enigmatic lake known today as Dombé Wari or “Dome Lake” (Rongmuthu, 2008. pp. 4-7).

2) *Wak aro Achak ‘The pig and the dog’*

This folktale describes the living beings living under a simple everyday life in the villages of Garo hills. The first living being depicted in the folktale is a pig described as “a hardworking animal who tilled the land as instructed by its owners, the old woman and the old man who looked after them as their own children” (Rongmuthu, 2008, p. 122). The second animal, achak ‘dog’ is defined as a creature “who was too lazy to do the chore and instead claimed that it did the work whereas in reality, it slept the whole day under the shade of a tree” (Rongmuthu, 2008. p. 122). The moral of the story is that one should not take credit for the hard work of others which is described by Sangma (1974, p. 27) as, “*Togiachi sakgipinko duko ga·akatna man·a. Sakgipinni dakgimin kamko sakgipin jak dangdikpae namgni ba rasongko man·a. Ukon wakni ja·kolo achak ga·dapa minga*” (Lies can bring harm to people. By claiming someone else’s work as their own might bring laurels to them but this can cause harm to the person who has actually done the work. Such act of cruelty is known

as the dog's footprint over the pig's hardwork).

3) *Asimalja 'The first sin of the first false swearing'*

The folktale *Asimalja* is described as Sangma (1984, p. 99) “*songo noko mande sian salo, mangon mang·sengan salo matcha chiko, mongma doko, buga ra·o songgimikan salnimna nangrongachim. Uko dakpagija an·tangna nanga kamkosa ka·skae maiba dal·bea a·selo ga·akgija mandekon 'Asi malja' ine aganronga*” (traditional practices and beliefs should be followed and adhered to by the people, be it observing of beliefs and traditional practices in order to avoid calamity in one's life). The summary of the folktale is: Long time ago, when the A·chiks (Garos) settled in a country known as A·song Saora Chiga Timbora, two men, Asi and Malja committed adultery with their nieces. When the people suspected them and charged them openly, they swore that they were both innocent and bit on the blade of the *mil·am* ‘two-edged sword’ to the effect that Asi claimed that if he was guilty, the tiger should kill him and devour him, while Malja claimed that if he was guilty, the elephant should destroy him. Thus, the next day, they were both killed according to the claims they both made. “From that day, the names of Asi and Malja became terms among the A·chiks connoting sin and death due to deliberate sworn lies. The A·chiks believe that the word *Asimalja* denotes unlucky or ill-fated destiny or luck among those who commit sin and swear their innocence” (Rongmuthu, 2008. p. 89).

B. Negative Behaviors towards Nature

4) *Mongma aro mande 'The Elephant and man'*

There was a man in one village who was not afraid of elephants. One night, a rogue elephant came to his rice fields and ate all the rice grains from his field and trampled on them. In order to stop the rogue elephant, he came up with a plan. He braided the hay from his field and waited for the rogue elephant to return to his fields in the evening. After having his dinner, he lighted the braided hay and waited

for the rogue elephant. When it got darker, the rogue elephant returned to his field to eat the rice grains. Upon seeing the elephant, the man tied the burning haystack to its tail. The elephant got shocked and started trumpeting loudly in pain and also started running away. The man followed behind the elephant and kept on burning the haystack and that kept on burning the elephant. It is thus believed that to this day, the elephant did not return to his field because it was burnt badly. The moral of the story is that those who are brave can prevent bad things from happening to them as illustrated by Sangma (1984, p. 60) as “*ka·dongachi bang·a namgnirangko man·a*” (many benefits can be reaped by bravery). But at the same time, this folktale shows cruelty towards animals by setting a trap for them.

5) Muniko Man·chengani/The Appropriation of Muni: The Amulet

The moral of the folktale is described as Sangma (1984, pp. 1-5), “*simsakejaode an·tangni man·giminko gimaata, dal·bea bobil ong·ani a·sel sokoba meligrikaniko dakan kusi ong·grikipil·ani ong·a*” (if we are not careful, we can lose what we already have and that we need to live with each other and with nature in harmony so that we can help each other out in times of need). This folktale can be described as: A man named Niba Jonja once shot a bird. The bird fell at Aje Gilje’s home. Aje Gilje awaited his retrieval of the bird. When Niba Jonja arrived in pursuit of the bird, she enticed him rather than handing it to him. She got him inebriated, got him into bed, and they wed. Niba Jonja went to the weekly market one day, tripped over the Muni plant, and then dozed off for a while. He was awakened when Misi Beari Katchi Susime came upon him and informed him that the plant he had tripped over was a Muni plant or amulet and that he should carry it with him. Everyone slept when Niba Jonja brought the Muni plant to the market and brought whatever he pleased. Salgra, who was Aje Gilje’s uncle, visited them during his absence. The uncle then had an affair with his niece. Niba Jonja discovered it upon his return home and vowed to seek revenge. The Sun-God was called Salgra. Boulders rolled down when the light crossed the threshold as Niba Jonja waited in front of it. Niba Jonja fled to

hide because he was afraid. He was instructed to bury the Muni plant by Misi Beari. Niba Jonja followed the instructions. Salgra dozed off when he stepped on the plant. There was no light for a very long period. Earth's inhabitants suffered because of this. So, Niba Jonja was instructed to make amends by Misi Beari. When he did, everything returned to normalcy.

C. Descriptions of Nature

6) *Sal aro Jajong*

Asima Dingsima was the mother of the Sun and Moon. Rengra Balsa was the name of the Sun, and Bire Jite was the name of the Moon. The Moon used to be more attractive and dazzling than the Sun. When the mother wasn't home, they used to argue. One day, the Sun lost his temper over a trivial matter and spat dirt in the face of the Moon. To prove to the mother, the Moon remained without cleaning the face. When the mother saw it, she chastised the Moon for not cleaning and condemned his beauty and brilliance which grew dim, causing the mud to remain on its face even today. However, the Sun became brighter. Sangma (1974, pp. 27-28) summarizes the moral of the story as "*Togia aro tol·ako u·isona neng·bea aro uarangni kamranga bang·a dukrangko ga·akatronga. Ukon ku·siko bija bitchi okningo matcha bisi ine agana*" (it is hard to predict what calamity will happen due to lies told by others and that is why those who lie and cause harm to others with their lies are known as a person who has honey on their lips but tiger poison in their bellies).

7) *Jajongko Ra·ani 'The taking of the moon'*

Rongmuthu (2008) describes *Jajongko ra·ani* as "The staircase to the moon." In this folktale, the final words of the father who wanted to take the moon for his beloved child is illustrated as Sangma (1984, pp. 67-68), "*Jajongona sokna wa·chusa nangaijok, bakbak ka·sapae on·duatpaku*" (he needed only one more log of bamboo to reach the moon, however, the wife misunderstood him and chopped off the bamboo ladder

leading to his death). This folktale describes about doing the impossible without considering the consequences. It can be summarized as follows: The sun, moon, and stars were closer to us in the past than they are now. The parents of a son were relaxing one evening while the moon was full. The father was asked to bring the moon so the son could play. The son cried hysterically despite the parents' best efforts to distract him by talking to him about various things. So, the father created a ladder to the moon from his jackfruit tree. He instructed his wife to give him bamboos once he reached a certain height. The wife cut the ladder off because she assumed she had been asked to do so. The man was killed when the ladder collapsed in a heap. The broken - down ladder became stones and is still found in the village called Chotiapara in Goalpara district.

D. Fauna in Nature

8) *Kawatte Ku-dilgila 'The Tiger and the Pangolin'*

This folktale is elaborated as (Rongmuthu, 2008, p. 124), "A long time ago, there was a tiger that was unable to kill the pangolin due to its hard outer shells. Whenever the tiger attempted to prey on the pangolin, it would roll over into a ball and make it hard for the tiger to dig its claws into the ball shaped hard crust. One day, the pangolin proudly remarked that the tiger was extremely dull and that it only had to attack the pangolin while it lay stretched out idly on the ground. Without the knowledge of the pangolin, the tiger overheard the remark made by the pangolin. Thus, the next time they tiger preyed on the pangolin, it did exactly the same thing the pangolin had boasted about and killed it. Thus the moral of the story is to not boast and announce everything to the world lest they might take advantage of it. In the folktale, the fauna in nature are the pangolin and the tiger." This folktale is described as Sangma, (1988, pp. 15-16) "*an-tangni kratcha-gni ba signi kattarangko aganjojoe ja-mano kratcha-ani ba sianio ga-akgipa mandekon kawatte ku-dikgila ine agana*"

(those who keep talking and announcing their embarrassing moments or ways to kill them ends up falling in the trap of their own mouths).

E. Natural Living

9) *Wa-al 'fire'*

Rongmuthu (2008, pp. 205-212) explains: “In the early days, the people had no knowledge about fire. They had no concept of cooking with fire at all. They ate all the food raw. One day, the mother of Susime felt sorry for the people because they ate everything raw. Thus she sent a *mat* ‘squirrel’ to fetch the fire from the depths of the earth because the fire was kept inside the depths or the core of the earth. The squirrel went to the depths of the earth and brought the fire by lighting its tail on fire. But since the fire burnt its tail, the squirrel could not bring the fire to the surface of the earth. He threw the fire halfway. Because the fire burnt the squirrel’s tail, the people believe that there is a species of squirrel whose tail is red due to its tail being burnt. Since the squirrel could not bring the fire, the mother of Susime sent the *aringga* ‘monitor lizard’ to fetch the fire. It made a hole in its tail to bring the burning embers but the fire burnt its back and tail so it dived into the water to save itself from the pain. It seems the monitor lizard prefers staying in the waters to this day since it was scared of the mother of Susime and the fire. So *Susismema* ‘the mother of Susime’ sent her brother *Katchi Beari* who asked the fire if it wanted to come up to the surface of the earth. The fire told *Katchi Beari* that it feels shy to come up and instead told him to make fire from wood by creating friction of wood on wood to light a fire. And thus the people started using fire this way in the olden days.” The moral of this story is that one should keep trying with all his might until they get what they want. The folktale is summarized as Sangma (1988, pp.53-54) “*untalsa da-na kingking waldu ra-o kingkang salo wa-alko man-a ine agana*” (from that day onwards the fire came into being because of the friction of wood on wood).

10) *Dajipming Danggo 'Dajip and Danggo'*

Dajipming Danggo is a folktale whose moral of the story is “*aratgipa mande dukko grongninga*” (Sangma, 1988, pp. 57-58) which implies that trouble befalls those who are lazy. This folktale illustrates how Dajip and Danggo, two brothers-in-law, once carried salt, dry fish, and rice when they travelled to the monthly market. The sun was setting when they arrived at a particular waterway. So they made a nighttime halt there. The senior brother-in-law advised them to gather firewood for the night so they could stay toasty. However, the junior brother-in-law claimed that because the sand was warm, they could slumber there because he was tired. Before going to bed, the senior brother-in-law gathered the kindling and burned it. He was shivering while dozing in the outset because it took some time to burn properly. The junior brother-in-law slept restlessly in the tepid sand. The logs burned efficiently as night fell, providing the older brother-in-law with peaceful slumber. The younger brother-in-law made no response when he made a sound. So he went to see what was wrong. The sand grew cold and immobilized his body, causing the younger brother-in-law to lose sense. He had to be warmed up in the fire by the older brother-in-law. Instead of heading to the market in the morning, they returned home. This folktale shows that being aware of nature and listening to elders is always a good thing and could save lives.

Conclusion

Moral principles are crucial to human life. For children to understand right and wrong behavior, it should be introduced to them at a young age. We can draw the conclusion from the discussion above that we should listen to our elders and take heed to the advice given by other people as well as respecting nature and the flora and fauna in it. We should live in harmony with nature and at the same time have discernment between the correct and incorrect use of the abundance of nature, and it also serves as a warning against misusing it. We ought to be appreciative of what

we already have. To avoid becoming individuals who have forgotten who they are and where they came from, we must also remember where we came from.

After analyzing ten folktales from the Garo people, it can be seen that three of the folktales depict the human-nature interaction, two of them are about how people behave negatively towards nature, two of them describe nature, one is about living things in nature and two is about natural living. The connections formed by people with natural elements and their influences on one another are described in the folktales collected under the subject of human-nature interaction. These folktales provide explanations for how the natural world's splendors and circumstances affect human existence. Additionally, these folktales illustrate the close connection between nature and humans with some powerful illustrations, such as a plant putting people to sleep, and the relationship people can build with animals and nature.

When pre-schoolers read folktales, they may absorb good behaviors of listening and obeying the elders, taking care of nature and may want to repeat them in order to quell their interest. Another noteworthy finding in the texts is that all of the Garos folktales are set entirely in the natural world, with no mention of any man-made structures like cities, homes, cars, etc. Naturally, the folktales of the peoples who live in remote areas of nature away from populated areas take place in nature. The flora that appears in folktales is actual, living components of societies.

Bamboo, peepal and jackfruit trees which are found in abundance are prominent in the folktale. Even water bodies like lakes, rivers etc. are depicted in the folktales of the Garos. Children are taught stories by their parents, relatives, and other family members beginning with the day they are born. Children's social, emotional, and cognitive growth depends on these encounters, and they learn about the icons, role models, and lifestyle practices of their society as a result (Al-Jafar and Buzzelli, 2004). Each analyzed folktale was discovered to contain some remnants of the society that produced it. All cultures place a high value on concepts related to morality, the environment and nature. All cultures should strive to educate kids who

are considerate of the environment, sensitive to it, and willing to take action for it. Information learned in childhood is highly persistent. Children should therefore be exposed to folktales with moral values, protection of the environmental or natural themes at a young age. This is expected to help them form favorable attitudes toward the environment and to become better citizens.

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Exploring the Man-Nature Relationship through Kunzang Choden's *The Circle of Karma* and *Tales in Colour and Other Stories*

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Abstract

Bhutan, called the last Shangri-La, had remained isolated from the world till the middle of the previous century. The idyllic landscape, culture and tradition deeply rooted in the Buddhist philosophies and religious beliefs have provided this land its unique status of being a nation full of happy people. Even with rapid dynamics of the 21st century modernization, this land boasts of a culture built and practiced on the premises of sustainability and preservation of the local environment. This aspect is central to the everyday practices of the inhabitants of this land, especially the rural folks, as outlined by Kunzang Choden in her writings such as *Tales in Colour and Other Stories* and *The Circle of Karma*. While narrating the voices of women through her writings, Choden presents to the world the uniqueness of Bhutanese folk-life that is imbued with a simplified lived reality of spiritualism. Her characters are ordinary women and men would explore their worth and identity, but not in the 'modern' sense of the term. The sustainability of nature and beliefs and allegiance to religion remains at the core of their existence, almost becoming the governing element of their identity. The stability of their mental dynamics too remains so enviable, that even a delirious woman seems convincing and peaceful to the readers. Folk knowledge and wisdom exhibited by the simple, uneducated rural folks, mostly women, almost seem like Choden's idea to question the necessity of modern, Western education. This paper attempts to ponder over the uniqueness of the ordinary problems experienced by Kunzang Choden's characters who cohabit with nature with a sense of spiritual unison. The Bhutanese people, especially women's role and unwavering dynamism towards nature imbued to its core with the folk belief systems, the interrelationship of the personal with the natural, the national fascination with isolation etc are some of the ideas that will be addressed by this paper.

Keywords: Bhutanese Women, Kunzang Choden, Sustainability, woman and nature, modernization and landscape

Kunzang Choden is the first women writer from Bhutan to write in English. Her first novel *The Circle of Karma* (2005) has opened up the new, unexplored domain of Bhutanese literature to a wider readership. Her second book *Tales in Colour and Other Stories* (2009), a collection of short stories has acted as an addition to the unique life-style of Bhutanese people in general and women in particular. Both the books present to the readers the idyllic landscape, culture and tradition of the Bhutanese folk-life, deeply rooted in the Buddhist philosophies, correlating religious beliefs and a deep attachment with and dependence on nature. These characteristics are central to the everyday practices of the inhabitants of this land, especially the rural folks, as outlined by Kunzang Choden in her works. Even while Bhutan is coping up with a sudden negotiation (since the country opened up its doors to modernity only a few decades ago) with the 21st century global modernization, the land still boasts of a culture built and practiced on the premises of sustainability and preservation of the local environment. The sustainability of nature and beliefs and allegiance to religion remains at the core of their existence, almost becoming the governing element of their identity. The enviable stability of their mental dynamics is a reflection of these inherent foundations. The sense of loss and confusion that the characters of Choden face at times, is not usually in their familiar homeland, but when they make transitions out of it. But there is, always, one element or the other from their own systems to turn back to, in case of such confusions. Therefore, these transitions are often reluctant, taken up only when absolutely necessary. Both of her books, *The Circle of Karma* and *Tales in Colour and Other Stories*, almost seem like Kunzang Choden's idea to question the necessity of modern, Western education, while there is always a strong religious-cultural belief system to turn back to.

The Circle of Karma tells the story of Tsomo, a young Bhutanese woman who embarks on the difficult and lonely journey of life. Tsomo's travels, which begin

after her mother's death, take her away from her family, and lead her across Bhutan and into India and back to Bhutan. Throughout the journey, a strong teenager Tsomo transforms into a coveted lover to a deserted middle-aged woman who, through a life full of adversities and struggles, finally completes the circle of Karma. Tsomo walks the path of life mistreated, illiterate, diseased and unequipped. But she remains true to herself and clears her karma within the same lifetime. The novel, as the title suggests, keeps echoing the Buddhist idea of karma time and again, and presents to us the rural, uneducated woman's perception of it through life realizations. From a separate point of view, Choden presents the idea of Karma as a real, lived experience of any ordinarily lived human life, not as something to be sought after foregoing all attachments. As no Karma is paid off without pilgrimages, the writer outlines a pilgrimage route (physical as well as figurative) for her protagonist, whereby the ordinary Tsomo gets on the path to enlightenment, with a heart full of forgiveness and empathy. While paying off her karmic debts, her ordinary human nature proves the strongest element towards her nirvana.

While documenting Tsomo's journey, evoking the question of instability caused by external factors, which are most often corruptions caused by urbanization and modernization, in the less-trodden virgin lands and landscapes of Bhutan, Choden also documents the changes in the life and concerns of the people of Bhutan on the wake of modernization influenced by Western ideas. Modernisation in Bhutan is not a gradual process. It is very sudden, since Bhutan has opened its doors to modernity only very recently to a world which is already pacing fast towards a common global urbanity. From narrating how simple minds are being intimidated and corrupted by development activities such as road-constructions, to raising the predicament of the older generations regarding their rehabilitation when the large families are breaking into nuclear families, Choden is trying to cover in her book almost all the questions that a contemporary Bhutanese seems to be dealing with. However, in this novel she is not only showing what the 'foreign' is doing to Bhutan, but also how a 'Bhutanese' is coping in foreign lands and the complexities of metropolitan spaces like Delhi.

The Tales in Colour and Other Stories present to the readers the new realities and identity issues that confront the contemporary Bhutanese women, her protagonists, and the challenges they face when their tradition-bound close-knit family life is suddenly disrupted by the elements of modernity, such as Western education, fashion, office jobs, even television etc. “Bhutanese women have always enjoyed a comparatively favourable status on a regional context as they have never suffered many of the gender based prejudices and discriminations endured by their sisters in the South Asian Region. We are now at a crucial stage in our transition, and we must not let go of our hold on our traditional archetypes of strong and independent women.” (Choden, 2009, p.5) is how Choden introduces her short stories in *Tales in Colour and Other Stories* (2009). Choden’s simple narration of these stories attune the readers with the simplicity of the life lived by the rural Bhutanese women. However, this simplicity of narration is almost deceptive, as they present issues which are in no way as simple as they sound. They show how ordinary lives, choices and experiences are both remarkable and poignant. The young girl in “I won’t ask Mother” suddenly feels empowered and confident when she makes a decision to get education without consulting her mother, or the protagonist of “Look at Her Belly Button” tries to assert a balance between her upgraded glamorous urban identity and the reality of a hardworking rural woman. All the stories take place in rural settings, to which creeping urbanization brings gradual change, and tensions surface between the new and the old, or the traditional and the modern, the institutional and the non-institutional. The question of power is very quietly dealt with by Choden through her characters, through means such as choice-making, education, fashion, customs, and resistance, at times even through delirium or disregard. There’s a strong sense of community life flowing through the stories. For example, in one of the stories, the villagers do not turn in a thief because mutual interdependence is recognized and respected by all.

Modernity, in the favoured sense of the term, had entered Bhutan somewhere during the last decades of the previous century. For a very long time Bhutan has

been protected from outside influences. The country was closed off from tourism until 1974; Television and internet were banned until 1999. The tryst with modernity is marked by Choden in her writings in numerous ways. *The Circle of Karma* depicts the idea first through the roadworks and the conditions of the migrant workers. She exhibits the loss of the flora and changes in the landscapes too. But at the same time, she very plainly projects to the readers a picture of the tryst: while modernization changes the aspirations of the people, especially the poor, struggling rural folks, it at the same time, goes against the philosophy of the nation, to remain one with nature. However, Choden, in a very un pitying manner, gives us the real picture of change, while she explores how modernization has worked as a means of empowerment for the rural women. To emphasize the contrast between the old and new world, she compares the rural and urban life, and successfully projects the unavoidable attachment with nature on the face of growing consumerism, which is built not only in the religious or cultural belief systems, but also in the psyche of the rural folks. For most of them, modernity is just an option; not to be exercised at the cost of nature which is the foundation of their collective psyche. That is why, TsewangDoma, in “Look at Her Belly-Button” (2009) returns to her village to work on the fields, to draw the manure, even after leading the life of an urban sophisticate with a rebellious belly button.

In the story, “The Woman Who Lost Her Senses” (2009) Choden uses Buddhism as a migratory religion and the advent of Buddhism is projected as process of modernization of the indigenous. Her female protagonist in the story is the victim and the survivor of the process. The mother of the protagonist, who was medium of the indigenous Bon tradition, gets labeled as a rebel in the newly established sect of Buddhism. And the protagonist Keba Lhamo represents the transition phase. The tryst with institutional (represented by a male Lama) and the non-institutional religion (a female medium of Bon tradition) leaves behind a generation which is confused, failing to identify their belongingness. Hence we see ‘the woman who lost her senses’, a woman, who was supposed to be keeping the tradition alive, being

declared as a mad woman. Thus, gender difference becomes an issue introduced by modernity as well, especially in rural environments.

Kunzang Choden, as a writer speaking on behalf of the women of the country, presents to us a mosaic of womanhood; her protagonists are all women and any woman. Her female protagonists range from delirious or drunk women to protective daughters, embarrassed daughters, deserted wives, scheming wives to single mothers who adopt any means to raise the children, to physically challenged woman. In “I Won’t Ask Mother” (2009) Yeshimo envisions an empowered life to make decisions on her own with the help of education. But at the same time she is confused to see her educated friend being paid salaries in her office for practically doing nothing, at least in comparison to the manual labour that Yeshimo does within the course of a day at her home. “The Advisor” (2009) presents a woman rejected by her husband becoming the self-proclaimed advisor of village until, after death, she becomes able to pull in the deserting husband. The empowerment for this protagonist is not being the advisor to the villagers, but in accomplishing what she desired, even at a supernatural level. This oneness with the supernatural is also an important facet of the Bhutanese rural life. “These Things Happen” (2009) explores the nuances of beauty as an empowering factor. Very plainly, Choden presents how beauty may make a woman empowered over man or the society, but it may lead to unethical or ruthless actions that disturb the harmony amongst the simple folks; in this case, between two neighbouring families living in complete harmony until false empowerment disrupts it. “I Am Like This” (2009) is about Lemo, who was once a highly admired singer and dancer, embarrassing her daughter by getting drunk at a cremation ceremony. Here Choden criticizes the unapologetic society that does not own up to its deeds towards unassuming simple women.”Mother of a Thief” (2009), as opposed to the successful single mother of “The Photograph” (2009), presents a woman who encourages her son to steal things as long as he doesn’t get caught. As he grows up, he continues to be the village thief, but for the sake of village harmony no one punishes him. In “I Am a Small Person” (2009), a hunchbacked, deformed

dwarf woman remembers the hardships of her life on her deathbed and mourns her inability to have a child. In “The Mouse in the House” (2009), a woman and a mouse live together in uncomfortable harmony. But then one day the constant nibbling by the mouse become too much for the woman and she decides to set a trap. This story, unlike the other stories, presents to the readers a glimpse of a life loaded with similarities with folktales. In “A Letter and a Note” (2009) Lhamo’s philandering husband resurfaces in a letter asking her to join him in Thimphu with the children. The title story, “Tales in Colour” (2009) is about an old woman, who is a master dyer, explaining to the younger generation. The story presents the dejection of a master craftswoman suffering from old-age dementia and how she desperately tries to pass on the craft, even with her failing memory.

In all of these stories from *Tales in Colour and Other Stories* as well as in the novel *The Circle of Karma*, Kunzang Choden, while trying to make both the books as ethnographic documents, does not deviate from the human-nature relationship that is lived by the Bhutanese communities, particularly by women. Although women are not projected as representing nature as such, but they are projected as close associates, victims and survivors of modernism at the same time, just like nature. And Choden draws effective parallels of both of the entities, namely woman and nature, through the stories she had woven. In *The Circle of Karma* she blends the concepts of womanhood in the face of patriarchy, nature in the face of modernity, with a pinch of the philosophical (more than religious) dimensions of the idea of karma as a lived experience. In *Tales in Colour and Other Stories*, she digs out similar issues in a wider and deeper sense. She blends spirituality and the supernatural, modernity and the religious, delirious and the tragic, the mundane and the ambitious, all together in the same platform. These stories almost seem like her attempt to question modernity and its supposed necessity in the self-sufficient oneness that the rural woman have with nature and the natural. This attempt gets highlighted with her usage of the simplest language and narration, possible only for the non-sophisticated rural people, leading ordinary lives and leaving extra-ordinary, hard realities.

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Re-presenting Realities: A Study Based on Selected Folk Tales from Kerala

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Abstract

This paper aims to study the question of representing realities in folk tales, with reference to selected folk tales from Kerala. Since time immemorial, folktales have been entwined with the cultural, social and historical fabric we are acquainted to. They have always existed as outlets to disseminate our fears, dreams and wildest fantasies. On this ground, folk tales could be analysed as a vehicle of deviation. Commonly understood as the representations of cultural continuities and complexities, they could also be understood as re-presentations of the worlds from which they originate. This very act of transforming reality, through imagination, has, over years, produced numerous folktales that challenge or question the realities we represent or that get represented through us. Re-exploring the possibilities of life, death, natural and the unnatural, they can be said to have re-conceived the world on much broader and accommodative grounds. In fact, in these post-pandemic times, these tales could also be re-read as tales of existence, cooperation and harmony, between humans and the forces of nature. Having lived through a crisis where even a minute virus forced us to re-conceive and re-live our realities, these folk tales could be re-understood as modalities that prophesied the need of a re-examination. The standpoints of theorists including V.P Anikin and Vladimir Propp have been studied to analyse the possibilities of the aspect of re-presentation. Shklovsky's theory of defamiliarization has also been used to support this argument. Three Malayalam folk tales, *Mannankattayum Kariyilayum* ("The Lump of Earth and the Dry Leaf"), *Vellappakshi* ("The Waterbird") and *Maṣḥadaivavum Muṣḥukkuḍiyanum* ("The Rain God and The Hopeless Drunkard") have been used to facilitate the study.

Keywords: reality, deviation, re-presentation, imagination, nature

Stories have always fascinated mankind. The pre-historic paintings found on the walls of ancient caves point towards the age-old relation between humans and stories. In the bygone eras, stories were not just aimed for recreation. They were considered powerful enough even to purify sinned minds, and liberate unsatisfied souls. In a world, where illiterates outnumbered the learned, story-telling helped immensely in the spread of common knowledge. The argument that stories originate from societies, where life has turned miserable, could also be read alongside this claim.

Folktales are stories that are not bound to a specific temporal or spatial scale. They originated from ancient man's imagination and life experience. These tales helped readers in understanding the ways, mores and morals concerning a society. Joy, sorrow, disappointment, love, anger, optimism, courage, adventure, victory, sympathy, intelligence, deception-all are disseminated through the medium of folk tales. They converse directly with the society they represent. They can serve as modalities that liberate humans from the cruelty and crookedness of the world they inhabit. Humans, trying to flee from the lived realities of their own stories, hunt for those where they are at last free. They try to overcome the odd experiences life gifted them through these tales. The innate tendency within humans to make their own lives more tolerable and pleasant, through the creation of a parallel world, where life is different, could be the reason for the development of folk tales. They are also committed towards the initiation of morality in the minds of the reader. Still, the tone of these tales is not essentially didactic.

India has a very rich tradition of folktales. Many renowned tales that were celebrated across the globe are said to have originated from India. The fables of Aesop, which has been orally propagated in ancient Greece for ages, share features with tales from the East. In the Buddhist and Jain traditions, stories centred around animals and insects are common. A notable collection of fictional stories in Sanskrit, 'Panchatantra' serves as an example. The characters featured in folk tales can include

ghosts, animals and birds. However, they serve as representations of the human mind and its intricacies. Hence, they have always been meant for the readers to communicate with their own selves. Arabic folk tales also feature a similar kind of narrative where animals and birds behave like humans. In order to delineate the aspects of re-presenting realities through folktales, three folktales from Malayalam have been studied.

Theorists like V.P Anikin and Lenin has studied and commented upon the representational aspects of folk tales. According to V.P. Anikin (1959), “Immediate social and historical

experience is the source of faithful representation of reality in folklore” (p. 70). He was trying to understand animal tales as allegories concerning class struggle. He has in fact remarked, “Social allegory is a most important feature of animal tales, and without it the people would not need the folktale” (Anikin, 1959, p. 70) Lenin’s opinion on the representation of reality in folktales is also worth mentioning here. He has said, “In every folktale there are elements of reality” (Lenin, 1962, p.19). According to Vladimir Propp, characters of a folk tale take shape from life. Propp, in his theorizing of represented realities in folktales takes special care in analysing Lenin’s standpoint. According to him, Lenin’s take on folktales is focused on its presence only, not on its omnipresence. Propp (1984) writes, “However, if we examine Lenin’s words more closely, we will see that, in his opinion, folktale does not consist entirely of elements of reality. He said only that they are present” (p. 18). Thus, it can be said that reality in its entirety need not be visible in folktales, but it will be presented, in a different pattern. According to Propp (1984), “one of the characteristics of folktale is that events that did not occur and could never have occurred are recounted with certain intonations and gestures, as though they did actually take place, although neither the teller nor the listener believes the tale” (p.19).

Reality is not just represented, but they are re-presented in folktales. The idea of ‘re-presentation’ can point to the ways in which folktales can deviate from life experiences, nonetheless take elements from it to distort the commonplace

experience of life, and present it in unfamiliar ways. The three selected folktales, in this sense, have elements taken from human world, but they are happening in a parallel world, where birds can cook and trees can speak. Thus, it can be said that the folktales are engaged in an endeavour to challenge our perception of the world in which we live and thus rebuild our conception of the same in unfamiliar ways. The theory of defamiliarization can be used to support this argument. The term ‘defamiliarization’ was introduced by Russian formalist Victor Shklovsky in his essay “Art as Technique”. For him, art is that technique which makes the familiar seem unfamiliar. He notes, “The purpose of art is to impart the sensation of things as they are perceived and not as they are known” (Shklovsky, 1916, p. 16). Thus, he considers art as that medium which helps us to re-awaken into our own worlds, but with a different perception. When applied to folk tales in which the normal order of the world is disrupted, defamiliarization serves to highlight certain aspects of human behaviour, society and culture. The selected folktales, are indeed working towards this ‘re-awakening’- towards new sensibilities, perceptions and ways of life. By anthropomorphizing animals and non-human entities, these folk tales provide a lens through which human characteristics and social dynamics can be examined from a different angle. The familiar traits associated with humans are here attributed to animals, and thereby defamiliarized. This in turn results in effects such as humour, satire or moral instruction. Defamiliarization in folktales also challenges the anthropocentric view of the world, and represents one in which humans are no more the centres of power.

Mannankattayum Kariyilayum
(“The Lump of Earth and the Dry Leaf”)

It is the tale of a pilgrimage undertaken by two friends, the lump of Earth (*Mannankatta*) and the dry leaf (*Kariyila*). Strengthened by the bond of the relationship they share, these friends are ready to tackle any crisis they will have to face on their way. In the beginning, as the wind blows, the dry leaf becomes worried. The lump

of Earth manages to assure him, “Don’t worry about it, my friend. No matter how strong the wind becomes, you will be safe as long as I am with you” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 42). As the wind blows, the dry leaf overcomes it with the help of the lump of Earth who steps over him. On moving further, it starts to rain. When the dry leaf gets worried, his friend assures him, “Didn’t you save me when the wind blew? Likewise, I will save you from the rain, without a doubt” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 42). The dry leaf climbs over the lump of Earth and saves it from dissolving in the rain. As the story ends, rain and wind strike together. “The lump of Earth and the dry leaf embrace” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 43) each other to be saved. At the end, “the lump of Earth melts into the rain” and “the dry leaf gets carried away by the wind” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 43).

The story which begins like a pleasant tale of friendship, ends in a dark, sinister note. The friendship depicted in the story is intended to cast an everlasting impression in the minds of the readers. The moral is intended to inspire a world where relationships are operating around principles of utility and self-centredness. Though the friends were determined to tackle the toughest of times, they were beaten at last by the powers of nature. Overthrown by the hands of nature, the friends’ hands are clasped together, till that very last moment they see each other. Here, the dry leaf and the lump of Earth stand as representatives of humans, their innate nature to bond with fellow men, their hidden fears, their little efforts to overcome the same, and finally the inevitable fate they could not defeat. The sacred journey they undertake is slowly becoming a journey towards death.

This story can be read alongside Nissim Ezekiel’s poem “Enterprise”. The poem features a group of travellers on a pilgrimage. Bonded together by determination and devotion initially, the group gradually starts to develop fractures along the lines of distrust and unrest as they move further. Finally, as they reach their destination, the pilgrims are reduced to “a straggling crowd of little hope” (Ezekiel, 2020, line 22), deprived of even their basic needs. Ezekiel’s story highlights the metaphorical journey of life, where the initial stages of innocence will slowly lead to stages of

disillusionment and dejection. The noble aspirations that bring together individuals initially would wither away as life take unexpected turns. At a deeper level, the unsuccessful journey of the travellers could be placed alongside the unsuccessful journey narrated in the tale. But the extent to which the latter becomes ‘unsuccessful’ is debatable. Their journey was doomed not because of any flaw from their side. Despite the team possessing admirable qualities, they were unable to withstand the wrath of nature.

On the one hand, this tale could be re-read as one which reminds human beings of their powers to accomplish motives, even by tackling the powers of nature. As one can see in the poem, it is not a natural force that stops the travelling group. In fact, the crowd was determinate enough to stand the forces of nature, represented through the raging sun. (“The sun beat down to march our rage/ We stood it very well” (Ezekiel, 2020, line 5) and a desert patch. Hence, it is only issues among themselves that hinders the journey. If the lump of Earth and the dry leaf had the amenities and the physical characteristics of the travelling group, they could have reached their destination easily. Here, the readers are presented with their lived reality in a fresh manner—they are made to re-think about their lives, where feelings of mutual trust, and love could make life easier, and world a better place to live.

***Vellappakshi* (“The Waterbird”)**

It is the tale of a Shikra bird who decides to prepare a *payasam*¹ for himself, having observed an old woman’s craze for the same. After successfully preparing the dish, the Shikra spreads his wings and gets ready to taste the same. Unfortunately, “the steam from the hot *payasam* slightly burns his face” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 439) and wings, the latter resulting in a foul smell, making him wonder if *payasam* smelt so. Unable to stand its odour, “he dumps the whole *payasam*” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 439) into a nearby river. After some time, the Shikra “gets to taste a drop of the *payasam* left in the dish” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 439). Blinded by its flavour, he impulsively jumps into the river, hoping to get a taste of the *payasam*, and stops only after having

drunk the entire river. In order to prevent water from draining out of his bloated body, he inserts twigs into the openings in his body. Fleeing from there, the Shikra at last reaches an outhouse, where a calf pulls out the twigs from the Shikra's body to feed on them. The tale ends in a note of utter tragedy as the water gushing out from the Shikra's body floods the whole neighbourhood.

The story is considered to be humorous tale, with no larger moral concerns embedded within. However, the dark note in which the story ends is notable. The tale could be probably hinting towards the moral that greed makes man blind and foolish, making him an easy prey for death. Here, the supposedly humane qualities are attributed to a bird. He efficiently observes the details of making the *payasam* and prepares one for himself. Another important aspect that makes the story noteworthy is that it features both human and non-human characters in the same canvas. In the previous story, the lump of Earth and the dry leaf were the only characters present. But here, the old woman, her son and the owner of the outhouse appear as human representations. The greed of the bird is to be juxtaposed with the greed of the old woman. It is in fact the sight of the grandmother gorging upon the *payasam* each day that triggers the taste buds of the bird. The bird's insatiable hunt for the taste ends him up in foolish situations, and ultimately a probable death. Adding to the factor of greed is the calf's desire to feed on the twigs. Thus, the story could be said to have re-presented reality in a different way.

Placed against a backdrop where the world is still grappling with the after effects of a deadly virus and its variants, the moral projected in the story could be even more thought-provoking. Humans were reduced to state of utter helplessness in the face of a deadly virus. Man's unconquerable pride and greed was answered by nature, as people all around the world could do nothing, but lock up themselves within their houses. Food, health, wealth, education- all possessions humans prized forever were under threat. Moreover, for the state of Kerala, having struggled under the pangs of two major floods, the story could take a different dimension. The greed of the bird which ended up in a flood could be re-interpreted along the cause-effect line as far

as the case of Kerala floods are concerned. Thus, the lived experiences of the world at present, could be said to have been re-presented in this tale in a prophetic tone.

Mazhadaivavum Muzbukkudiy anum
(“The Rain God and The Hopeless Drunkard”)

This is the tale of a hopeless drunkard, who drains a palm tree in his village every evening, by incessantly drinking toddy from it. Having had enough with the drunkard, one day, “the palm tree decides to put an end to his antics” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 460), with the help of his friend, the gentle breeze. The breeze, unable to stir the drunkard from the palm, transforms into a storm and takes him along. Later on, as the drunkard’s foul smell begins to flavour the breeze, he hands the former to his friend, the river. The river’s initial enthusiasm wanes away as “the drunkard’s stench spreads across the river” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 462). His friend, the rain comes to his rescue at the moment. As time passes, the rain, vexed by the drunkard’s callousness, tries to shake him off. With unwavering determination, he climbs up the raindrops, and reaches the Rain God. Incidentally, the Rain God turns out to be another drunkard, who follows the protagonist to his village as he details the flavour of the toddy available there. Finally, the irritated palm tree, now having to get rid of not just the hopeless drunkard, but the God as well, seeks the help of none, but the drunkard himself. The latter is promised that he “will be fed forever with as much toddy as needed” (Sreekumar, 2010, p. 464) if he can get rid of the God. The crafty drunkard mixes a powder in the toddy, after which the God’s throat burns in pain, making him flee from the spot. As the story ends, the palm tree, impressed by the drunkard’s resourcefulness, decides to feed him forever.

Just like the tale of the waterbird, this story is popular as a tale of humour. But, deeper levels of meaning can be discerned from the same. The central theme of the story is drunkenness. The story steps out of the conventional ways of moralizing against the practice, and in fact ends as the drunkard continues to be so, now with the added advantage of having impressed the palm. The parallel world is one where

even God is a hopeless drunkard. However, the tale could be re-read as a scathing satire on man's indulgence on self-destructive ways of life. The God's state of inebriation might be indicative of the ways in which this indulgence is encouraged and celebrated even by people who are in power, who could probably do something to put an end to it. On the other hand, the story could also be re-invented as a reminder of human abilities, just like the story "The Lump of Earth and the Dry Leaf". The hopeless drunkard is not just outwitting the forces of nature. He is in fact, making them to surrender in front of him. The palm tree, the gentle breeze, the river, the rain and the Rain God-all the mighty forces of nature are just playthings for him. The story brings out humorously how a man's determination overcomes the challenges posed by different forces of nature. Drunkenness is here the Holy Grail for which the man is in search of. Had all the adventures and tactfulness been used for a much nobler cause, it would have improved the lot of humanity as such. The drunkard's incompetence to do that could itself be that point which reveals the absurdity and futility of human fascination for self-destructive ways of life. The story, by bringing out the desperate human inability to invest oneself for a productive action, reminds the readers of their innate ability to bring positive changes to the world around them, provided their capacities are used rightly.

Conclusion: Realities Re-presented

As we examine these folktales, it can be observed that our realities, of going on a pilgrimage, of cooking, and of drinking are served back to us in an unfamiliar way. The world got used to unfamiliar ways of life and living post 2020, after the global outbreak of the COVID-19. We are getting to deliberate the reality represented in the folktale with a different sensibility now, one that can give space to things we deemed unimportant earlier. Some common features could be selected from these tales to look at the ways in which realities are re-presented and lived life is re-told. In the first story, the destination, Kashi (now known as Varanasi) is a renowned pilgrimage site in India. In the parallel world depicted in the story as well, Kashi is

considered sacred. The journey of the two friends for spiritual rejuvenation, is the journey of humanity towards peace and harmony. Though no humans are present as such throughout the story, there are human realities present within. In the second story, incidentally, humans appear as minor characters. The parallel world's reality is one where non-humans are capable of solving their concerns of hunger. The reality of self-centred and utilitarian lifestyle of the human world is re-presented through the greed of the bird. In the third story, human power of wit and crookedness is juxtaposed with the physical powers of nature. The disturbing reality of alcoholism is a source of humour for the parallel world. This re-presentation could be satirical, intended to poke the senses of the readers. Thus, all the three stories are transforming lived realities, by challenging or questioning their mundane representations. They also serve as platforms for the re-exploration of the possibilities pertaining to life, death, the natural and the unnatural. The three stories where the human, the non-human, the natural, the unnatural, the living, the non-living and much more come together, can be considered as re-conceptions of the world on much broader and accommodative grounds. The mutual communication and harmony that exists between the natural and the human world is a feature notable in all the three stories. Re-reading these tales after 2020 gives them a different dimension. These are tales where deliberations concerning existence, cooperation and harmony, between man and the forces of nature are done, and are therefore seminal for our re-conception of a better place to live in.

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Endnotes

- 1 A South Indian dessert made using milk, ghee, jaggery and sugar.

Reading of Temsula Ao's Select Works: Conflicts in Cultural Assimilation

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Abstract:

North East India amalgamates vibrant cultures and diversities of different ethnic groups, communities, and tribes. The region circumscribes vivid regions with multilingual identities. However, this multicultural ethnicity of the North Eastern culture has aroused certain issues in recognizing one's identity and selfhood. Temsula Ao is one of the critically acclaimed writers of North Eastern Literature, especially notable for her prose and poetry collection. The present paper attempts to critically analyse and examine the conflicting crisis in the formation of identity through the reading of "Songs from the Other Life" (2007). Due to the hybridization of different cultural identities, the indigenesness reduces its prominence in creating an individual identity amidst the hybridization. Through the reading of Temsula Ao's poetry collection, it laments the loss of indigenous culture and identity. The poetry collection chosen for the paper reflects the indecisive chaos occurring into the minds of people while identifying between their indigenous identities and globalized counterparts. Her writings attempt to revive the cultural loss and preserve the nuances of the historical traditions and social orders of the ethnic groups and tribes of the North Eastern region.

Keywords: Culture, identity, hybridity, assimilation

Introduction

Temsula Ao has established herself having a major voice in Indian English Literature, a storyteller par excellence, a poet who sings of her life and that of her people. She has returned back to her roots to find its essence in the very unrealizability of that history that her people's troubled present arises; the dislocations and displacements have aroused their present turmoil.

Ao's latest collection of poems, "Songs from the Other Life" (2007) cements her status as the poet of her community. The poems articulate the Ao-Naga culture, history and the present. The epigraph to this collection is entitled as, "History" and says that the songs will "redraft history" and "augment of the lore" of the Ao-Naga's "essential core" (Ao, 2007, p. 239). North East India is prone to several insurgency movements and hence these states have often faced the brunt of peripheralization and marginalization by the Centre. The Ao community of Manipur had a unique and vibrant ethno-cultural identity before modernization set foot into it. In an attempt to westernize the place, it lost its blissful and enchanting culture. Tilottama Mishra states, "The invasion of an alien culture that lay exclusive claim to modernity and compels the indigenes to be apologetic about their own culture has been the subject matter of much of the writings from the region" (Sharma, p.4). Due to the politics of marginalization, the innocent and peace-loving Nagas were stripped off their original identity. Through meticulously seasoned manoeuvring, they influenced the indigenous people to bury their traditional culture. The Centre has also pushed the region to the margins due to non-conformity with the Centre. Eventually, as time lapsed, a dislocated culture is born, they have become voiceless subalterns who are denied their original identity and history. Baruah rightly says that, "'Northeast' is a representation of a forced homogenization or standardization that has resulted in a situation of deficit democracy" (2005, p. 23).

The writers of North East have been engaged in the process of "cultural revivalism", as they are aware of the loss of their indigenous culture. Literature is

a forum for them to lament, revive and preserve their histories and identities. This attempt can be seen in Temsula Ao's poetry collection, "Songs from the Other Life" (2007). The title of the collection suggests that these songs are from an 'other life'- a life that once was, but is no longer continuing. Ao states her objective behind penning down the poems- "to redraft history" in the epigraph of the collection, which is named History:

These Songs

From the other life

Long lay mute

In the confines

Of my restive mind

.....

.....

They now resonate

In words of new

Discernment

To augment the lore

Of our ancient core. (Ao, 2007, p. 239)

On one hand, Ao laments the fact that their culture and practices underwent several changes. Through "These songs", their history, beliefs, and traditions are passed down from one generation to another and form the very essence of their identity. However, it lays "mute" in their collective memory. On the hand, she says that it is not fully dead, but they now "resonate" with a new "discernment". Ben Okri once said: "we are part human, part stories" (Sharma, n.d., p. 5). This is quite true for the tribal nations, for whom oral history is of prime importance. The new generations pass their tradition with a new taste and parlance to suit their changing needs.

North East is an amalgamation of various tribes, cultures, food, and festivals, its way of living is different from the other states of India. The Centre failed to understand the beauty of these differences. In an attempt to homogenize these heterogeneous cultures, they have been segregated. This resonates Homi K. Bhabha's theory of "totalization of culture", which points to one's failure of understanding the diversity of the people, their place, and their culture. This leads to the fear of losing one's ethnic identity which, in turn, leads to a perpetual cycle of terror and violence. According to Ved Prakash, "In India's North-East, insurgency is an ethno-cultural phenomenon, in the sense that perceiving their ethnic identity threatened, they seek political power to preserve it..." (Sankhyan, 2016, p. 33). They are haunted by the feelings of rootlessness and ignominy and tend to segregate themselves as the pride tribes of the North-East.

Due to the modern approaches to life, the young generation failed to understand the beauty of their roots and age-old societal practices. Ao talks about the youth of Manipur and their irreverence for their traditions in the poem "Night of The Full Moon":

The youth had prevailed in the huddle
Where the new strategies were planned,
But some old ones are deeply disturbed
At what was resolved,
Because unlike such other nights
Tonight they walk
With no customary tributes
For their king. (Ao, 2007, p. 261)

However, Ao also states that though external forces like modernity compelled them to garb 'hybridized identities', the essence of their core remains unchanged. She seems to adhere to what Bhabha says in *The Location of Culture* (1994): "The effect of mimicry is camouflage... it is not a question of harmonizing" (p. 85). The

mythical “lion king” in the poem roars audaciously:

“We may have altered our name

But our person remains the same.” (Ao, 2007, p. 266)

Ao accepts that the preservation of cultures in their pristine and undiluted state is an impossibility. She also acknowledges that this results in the alienation of identities and cultural chaos.

In “Nowhere Boatman” she hints at this as she describes the ageless boatman who is stuck ‘on the river between/ two irreconcilable worlds’. Ao presents the conflicts and indecisiveness that occur in the minds of her people as they are hung in dilemma over choosing between their indigenous identities and their globalized counterparts.

She expresses deep concern about lost identities in the following lines:

A soul without status

Is how I see myself

...

What advantage

...

Of relocating well-defined souls

In preordained spaces

...

An ageless, nameless

Indispensable anomaly. (Ao, 2007, p. 246- 247)

The title itself is a paradox; the “boatman” is expected to lead the way, but the prefix “nowhere” brings in the very sense of directionless. It is a powerful poem that evokes the need for restoring the lost identities of the tribal community.

Easterine Kire in her essay, “Should Writers Stay In Prison?” (2011) commented “We do not celebrate invisibility. We fear and reject invisibility” (p.15). Just as

Rushdie's *Midnight's Children* writes back to the empire, Temsula Ao, writes back to "mainland India" and has succeeded in withdrawing the contemptuous attitude towards Northeast and its writers. Through her powerful voice and distinctive literature, she has triumphed in bringing Northeast out of the shadows of nameless anonymity and giving it a universal appeal.

Many of her poems carry an undercurrent of scepticism about the supposed civilization and refinement of the tribals brought about by the colonizers. She is also sceptical about the stigma and derision that has come to be associated with the indigenous ways of life. Ao projects the conflicts of cultural assimilation in another poem "Blood of Other Days", where she succinctly describes the advent of Christianity and the resulting hybridization of culture and "perfect mimics.":

Then came a tribe of strangers
Into our primordial territories
Armed with only a Book

She expresses how these people convinced the indigenous people that our Trees and Mountains Rocks and Rivers were no Gods
And that our songs and stories
Nothing but tedious primitive nonsense. (Ao, 2007, p. 297)

It was astonishing to see that despite the long-standing tradition, the people let strangers lead the way. They started to believe that their knowledge was insufficient and trivial. They were confused and started to doubt their own rituals and ancestral God. They were "Beguiled by the promise of a new heaven" (Ao, 2007, p. 297). She laments how the present generation does not have the same reverence she had for the old customs and traditions. Her age was full of pride and admiration and highly respected their oral literature, myths, and legends. However, with the due course, she noticed that

My own grandsons dismiss our stories as ancient gibberish.

Who needs rambling stories

When books will do just fine?"

She recalls her grandfather who has warned

"That forgetting the stories

Would be catastrophic

We would lose our history,

Territory, and most certainly

Our intrinsic identity. (Ao, 2007, p. 241)

K.S. Nongkynrih commented that the missionaries gifted the tribals with a "common literary heritage" but at the same time, they robbed them of their own "literature" that was rich in "oral traditions". The tribals became victims and they were ashamed of their own heritage that was labelled as "pagan and preposterous" (Ngangom, 2009, p. 3). Easterine Kire appealed to the writers and readers to look beyond the conflicts and violence and delve into the lives of ordinary Naga people in her article, "The Conflict of Nagaland: Through A Poet's Eyes" published in 2004.

In "The Old Story Teller", Temsula Ao reiterates her role as keeper of her cultural heritage, "I have lived my life believing / Story-telling was my proud legacy" (2007, p. 240). Using flowing free verses, the poet starts out on an enthusiastic note acknowledging the responsibility that she shoulders of keeping her tradition alive. The poem begins in a casual style talking about how the poet inherited the legacy of story-telling from her grandfather and sidles gradually into its theme without much fanfare. A note appended to the poem explains the origin of the Oral Tradition of the Ao-Naga community. It maintains that in ancient times, the tribe possessed a script which was displayed on a hide for everyone to read and learn. However, a dog one day accidentally swallowed the hide and so the script was lost forever. Since then, the people have retained every aspect of their lives through the Oral Tradition (Ao,

2007, p. 240). The poem makes reference to the traditional myths about creation of the tribe and commonality of humans and animals. However, the tone turns apprehensive toward the end of the poem as the poet laments the new generation's disbelief in the cultural history of the tribe:

The rejection from my own
Has stemmed the flow
*And the stories seem to regress
Into un-reachable recesses.* (Ao, 2007, p. 240-242).

However, despite the despair of witnessing her tradition fade, the poet perseveres in resurrecting her legacy through her poetry. "Nowhere Boatman" is based on the Ao-Naga myth according to which the boatman is paid some coins to sail the souls of the dead from the Land of the Living to the Land of the Dead where they can continue their afterlife journey (Ao, 2007, p. 245). The title "Nowhere Boatman" is a paradox, as one expects the boatman to lead the way; however, prefixing the "nowhere" defies the very sense of direction it generates. The argument in the poem proceeds in a discursive manner with the boatman counter questioning his passengers and rejecting their answers one by one as in the following lines:

*They even ask me
How old I am
As if knowing my age has anything to do with
their being on my boat for their last ride
.....
I shall send the pesky souls to the tree-stump whose belly
Is now my boat, to tell them
How old is old?* (Ao, 2007, p. 219)

Through her ingenious craft, the poet manages to trace the origin of the tradition to nature itself and express the existential dilemma with apparent ease as in these lines:

Anyway, what has age to do with dying
And of what use this irrelevant knowledge
When they are already pledged
On a one way journey
To their destiny? (Ao, 2007, p. 219-220)

The tone of the poem turns sombre towards the second half with the poet empathizing with the insignificant existence of the boatman. The boatman turns sceptical about his own role of ferrying the dead to the after world and wonders if he'd ever be redeemed himself.

According to a Sangtam Naga legend, the beautiful Momola was loved by a fish-king. When her mother reneged on her promise to him in return for the plentiful harvest of fish, he always gave her; he threatened to destroy the entire village by a great flood. Momola was eventually sacrificed to the waves where she was transformed into a big fish with a distinctive white spot on her forehead. Ao has expressed her emptiness and alienation despite having people, love and affection around her as she verses in her poem, "The Other world" that, "...he is always with me. I am truly alone and in total disjunct"(Ao 2007, p. 256). However, the lonely feelings of displacement reflect distinctively in the poem:

*Obsessed and solely concerned,
With protective possessiveness,
The old king can never guess how much
I miss my misplaced world.* (Ao, 2007, p. 256)

Moreover, she feels the pleasant environment to be blurry and vague, dreamlike as the speaker can reminisce the terrible days where people breathed in terror and merciless execution of reckless promises. Inspired by a Naga myth about tigers, which says that on each full moon night all the tigers of a region gather at a designated spot to pay homage to their king, who happens to be the biggest one among them. On such nights when they gather to receive counsel from their King, they also bring

gifts of animals they have hunted, either whole or big portions thereof, as tributes to him. Through the verses of the poem “Night of the Full Moon”, Ao has expressed the disturbances created in the existing social orders and customary rights:

*The youth had prevailed in the huddle
Where the new strategy was planned
But some old ones are deeply disturbed
At what was resolved
Because unlike such other nights
Tonight they walk
With no customary tributes
For the King.* (Ao, 2007, p. 261)

Through the readings of Ao’s poems, it reflects the nuances of cultural assimilations created due to the terror lives of Naga Community, the people struggled to find a stable identity. As their social traditions and orders were at the hands of powerful controllers, their patriotic feeling to save their own social order and traditions deeply rooted into their retainment of Cultural norms. As a result, the conflict has occurred in understanding whether to accept or reject the newly introduced social orders or to remain intact towards their ethnic dogmas.

In one such poem of Ao published in *Book of Songs* (2007) entitled as “When a Stone Wept”, she has expressed the societal tensions and worries regarding their losing of native land by new species. According to an Ao-Naga myth the first Ao people, three males and three females emerged from six stones, at a place called *lungterok*. The Aos’ also say that certain big stones ‘give birth’ to small stones, which move away from human sight to grow and become big stones themselves to procreate, thus making sure that they dominate certain landscapes where no life can ever exist. Thus, Ao verses as:

*The womb of the young earth nestling
Beneath the huge stones heaved
Dislodging their foundations in expelling
Her secrets through phenomenal birth
After the great upheaval the stones stirred,
Anxious to establish permanent moorings
In a landscape they knew would soon
Be dominated by the new species.* (Ao, 2007, p. 271)

Sharma has mentioned in her paper entitled as “Temsula Ao as an Exemplary Contemporary Tribal Poet of Northeast India: A Reading of Selected Poems” that:

Temsula Ao’s poetry has brought Northeast out of the shadows of nameless anonymity. It has captured the imagination of the nation and has, to a large extent, succeeded in doing away with the injustice meted out to the literati of the Northeast. It has, to a large extent, triumphed in effacing the dismissive neo-colonial attitude of ‘mainland India’ towards the ‘tribals’ and the “tribal writings of Northeast (Sharma, n.d., n.p).

Naga Community and the native land is unique in its own social order, culture and traditions; thus, Ao pulls apart the “colorless homogeneity” (Sharma, p. 10), i.e. the homogenous construction of the region that is superimposed upon the region and speaks of its uniqueness and distinctive variety. Her writings can be compared to Rushdie’s *Midnight’s Children* that writes back to the empire. Temsula Ao, through her poems, writes back to ‘mainland India’ where the tribal writings are generally seen with contempt and a lack of interest. Her poems are an attempt to deconstruct and demystify the “tribal constructs and the tribal worldview that regulates their life” (Sharma, n.d., p. 10). The emerging writers from Northeast India, including Temsula Ao has projected a universal appeal, an ethnic specificity as well as aesthetic universality through their powerful words.

This similar sense of cultural sensibility can be seen in the poems of Robin S. Ngangom, a Manipuri poet and a writer. In his familiar poems such as “A Poem for Mother” and “The Strange Affair of Robin S. Ngangom”, he has expressed his emotional feelings and griefs towards the downfall of his native land at the hands of insurgent actions and as well the cultural and loss of natural bliss. He laments over the newly developed landscape of his native land filled with political environment of terror and horror showered with the bliss of gunshots, kidnapping and rape and death has become their ultimate beginning.

This view of growth and cultural development and assimilation has tormented the lives of the North Eastern region, especially the tribal poets who have been lost at the unpleasantness of Selfhood and nativity. Through the critical readings of Ao’s poems, it reflects the societal tensions and worries towards the dismantled order of their indigenosity and ethnicity under the surveillance of newly formed conquerors. In the poem, “The Last Hunt”, Ao has used her verses to portray the terror and horror sustenance of their livelihood. The community has also started taking up measure to protect their nativity and cultural homogeneity:

*It was not very long ago
When I saw the tell-tale signs
Of twilight feasting
Beneath the fruit-laden
Wild fig tree
And since then I had planned
To erect a machang nearby
To watch and hunt
The fattest stag that was devastating
My newly-planted paddy.* (Ao, 2007, p. 280)

The feelings and emotions towards the political upheaval and the cultural sensibility can be seen more distinctly to be aroused in her poem, “Trophies”.

This poem refers to the ancient Naga custom of Chopping off the heads of slain enemies in warfare and bringing them as trophies, for public display at a central place. Head-takers were considered to be heroes and such warriors earned the right to wear special ornaments, clothes and give Feasts of Merit to the entire village as a mark of their elevated status in society:

It is one of those crazy nights yet again;
The air is rent by bloody-curdling yells
Of the warriors come home
With enemy heads which will hang
From the skull-tree in the village field.
The heads will sway gently
With unseeing eyes, and hair
Matted by their own blood. (Ao, 2007, p. 284)

The poet laments about the loss tormented at the hands of the violent enemies, the punishment as a repercussion faced by the enemies shall not be enough to fill the losses the people have faced and thus, this resents them with a felling of anguish and hatred:

*I shall confront him and say,
'You may rejoice over your bloody trophies
But enemy heads will never fill
My child's empty belly,
Nor quench my need for a body
Untainted by another's blood
To douse the heat of summer
And ignite the cold of winter
And if you do not heed me
I may soon return to my parents
A widow and your son
The orphan of an irresponsible father.* (Ao, 2007, p. 286)

Ao's collection of Poetry from North-East India acquires a new height echoing some untold stories and myths deep rooted into the cultural ethnicity and indigenesness. In *Book of Songs: Collected Poems* by Temsula Ao, Ananda Bormudoi of Dibrugarh University comments,

“All her poems are short lyrics on a wide range of situations and events. They evoke different moods of the speaker or the singer, a dazzling array of mental configurations and dynamics. Though she writes on situations and particulars of the Northeast, the verse can also be read and interpreted as chronicling a general human condition. A reader feels the immediacy of these events, situations, and moods and their relevance to his or her life” (Ao, 2007, n.p.). Thus, as an ethnographer-poet, she has tried to restore and preserve the ethnicity of her community.

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The Materiality of Memory in Mamang Dai's Select Poems

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Abstract

This paper seeks to examine Mamang Dai's representation of memory as a material reality. Most of Dai's poems have a wide political acclaim as they vehemently try to carve out a distinct space for the socio-cultural reality of the Adi tribe of Arunachal Pradesh on the national map that otherwise is reluctant to grant it cultural legitimacy. In fact, one theme that runs throughout her oeuvre to bring out the history of her community is that of memory and remembrance of the cultural past. Memory constitutes an important part of the provincial ethos for the Adis. Memory is almost yielded as a tool which helps in the sustenance of community values on the one hand, and, on the other, in the fight against the new cultural inputs which often infringe upon them as contacts with the mainland grow. Dai particularly investigates how people of her like tackle problems that crop up when a tribal person migrates away from the homeland. The mnemonic aspect of culture constitutes an important part in the life of exiles as such.

Memory is often thought of to be an abstract element. She is aware of the dangers of how it is often assumed that memory (most often condensed as oral history of the tribe) is loosely hanging and inferior to written discourses. So, she has foregrounded materiality of memory in her poems. And when she is in exile, constantly threatened by majoritarian values infringing upon her native values and trying to obliterate them, she remembers the landscape of her homeland, the physicality of space, the elementariness of cultural practices to retain her identity. This paper, thus, will try to critically examine how Dai's poems like "Gone," "Floating Island," "Small Towns and The River," "The Voice of The Mountain," and "The Desire of Ink" explore the complicated interactions between the mainstream India and North-Eastern hinterlands through the perspective of a person from the tribe who has had to move out of his or her homeland to towns in the mainland and tries to remember his/her cultural past through the materiality of memory.

Keywords: Mamang Dai, memory, home & away, culture

Introduction

Literatures from the North East, produced from a liminal space located within an already marginalized developing country, tend to become a part of postcolonial resistance literatures. Certain specific political concerns frequent the contours of the poetry of the North Eastern India and that is why, the poets of the North East engage in dialogues with the predominant nationalist discourses. Some of their poems carry explicit reminders of the controversial making of states in the post-independence era. They also try to offer a literary resistance to the mainland's breaching into the virgin forests of their lands and other similar cultural intrusions. From the North East of India one can, thus, witness the emergence of a "genre of 'political' literature" (Zama, 2013, p. xvii) that sincerely engages itself with identity politics. The poetry of Mamang Dai, in this context, seems to be a great analogue because most of Dai's poems vehemently try to carve out a distinct space for the socio-cultural reality of the Adi tribe of Arunachal Pradesh on the national map that otherwise is reluctant to grant it cultural legitimacy as the Adis are conceived of as people inhabiting not the centre but the fringes. In fact, to do so, Dai's poems obsessively engage with the issue of memory and she keeps on showing how memory can act as an important politico-cultural tool to bring out the history of her community and effect the remembrance of the Adi cultural past. Memory, indeed, constitutes an important part of the provincial ethos for the Adis. This paper argues that this memory has a peculiar character which Dai especially keeps on highlighting: it is not psychic, abstract or intangible as memory is often thought to be but, instead, is very material. Constantly threatened by majoritarian values that infringe upon her native values and try to obliterate them, she foregrounds the materiality of memory by conjuring the landscape of her homeland, the physicality of space, the various beautiful forms of arts and crafts of the tribe and the elementariness of the Adi cultural practices to retain and assert her identity. She, in short, shoves the very

materiality inherent in the mnemonic-cultural treasures of the Adis in front of her readers.

The Mnemonic Turn and Materiality of Memories

Of late, there has been a proliferation of discourse and scholarship on memory; it is as if theory itself has taken a mnemonic turn. Rightly observes Klein (2000), memory, now, is almost like an industry (p. 127). The emergence of memory as a novel historical mediation is being attributed by numerous scholars to the recent crises faced by historicism: memory has gained a critical currency in the wake of a postmodernist challenge to ‘grand narratives’ that has led to a critique of the totalizing tendencies of historical discourse. Thus, memory seems to barge in the fault lines and crevices created by the limits of modern historical knowledge. Memory can no longer be used synonymously with history to humanize it. It is, in fact, contrary to history rather than being complementary to it. Memory prevents the forgetting and effacement of those traces of culture that tend to get buried under the heavy footprints of history. But then, given the abstract quality of memory as it conjured by a psychological choice made by the remembering person and the dubiousness concerned with questions, such as, who remembers and what does she/he remembers, it appears to be loosely hanging and erratic unlike written discourses. Mamang Dai, interestingly, seems to be aware of such insidious dangers because the mnemonic property of the Adi tribe predominantly comprises oral narratives and, this is why, perhaps, instead of focusing on its abstractness, she brings out the materiality of memory in poems like “Gone,” “Floating Island,” “Small Towns and The River,” “The Voice of The Mountain,” “Once Upon a Time in Pasighat,” and “The Desire of Ink.” In fact, while doing so, Dai also marks out the alienation of her tribe and its mnemonic culture from the monolithic historical narrative that has been consolidated in the Indian nationalist pedagogy.

The materiality of memory manifests itself when, as Nora (1989) observes, “memory crystallizes and secretes itself” (p. 7). Material memories have no external

referents, are things contained in themselves, and are a part of the immediate, physical reality. They do not just take the place of an anterior, absent thing. Rather, they always signify a live, physical encounter between people and the objects. This object-oriented approach to memory helps evasion of any aporia arising out of attributing to someone the act of remembering. The egological nuances of memory are cast aside in favour of memory that presents itself as souvenir before us; memory in its very flesh. Memory then becomes more than an affect that pops up in the mind and triggers a psychic process of recollection. Rather, its physicality stresses on the immediacy of its presence. Ricoeur (2009) claims that there are both cognitive and pragmatic sides to memory and material memory always slants towards the pragmatic side. Again, materials have a special claim on memory. Rightly observes, Terdiman (2018), “objects have an intimate relation to remembrance” (p. 13). When Mamang Dai received the Padmashree, YD Thongchi, President Arunachal Pradesh Literary Society said that Mamang Dai is strongly rooted in the soil of her native place (Thongchi, 2011, as cited in Vohra, 2013). Dai, indeed, has a passionate connection with her land and people; the mountains, the rivers and the clouds, that are typical of the Adi landscape. Thus, the intimacy shared between objects and memory is also shared by Dai and the Adi culture. This parallelism yields an interesting material-mnemonic layer to her poems.

Landscapes as Monuments

Dai’s poems containing a flurry of environmental and natural imagery seem to emblemize what Terdiman (2018) calls, “live, organic memory” (p. 30). In “The Voice of the Mountain,” it is interesting to observe that the poem’s speaker is the personified mountain and this rhetorical invention seems to condense the memory of animistic beliefs that has prevailed among the Adis since ages, in the rocky, material contours of the mountain (Dai, 2016). The poem also makes references to other elements from a gallery of geographical edifices like the canyon and the narrow gorge. The mountain also talks of a dream of “permanence,” compares

itself to “an old man sipping the breeze/ that is forever young” and claims its special status as a space where “memory escapes/ the myth of time”. Thus, Dai seems to argue that the mountain, the canyon and gorges qualify as material memory as they are the permanent cultural emblems of the Adi landscape and are free from the temporality of time because of their localizability in space. The materiality of the mountain also by making the Adi territory “forever ancient” and reeking with memory, seems to safeguard the past that the people of Dai’s tribe nourish, despite several mainland interventions. It is as if the mnemonic traces of Adi culture as Dai’s metaphor suggests are the “particles of life” that cling to the material body of the rocky, hilly landscape. “Gone,” talks about the monumentality of a “burnt black hill” (Dai, 2018). So, the landscapes no longer remain environments which evoke memory but become the sites of memory. Dai’s poem, in fact, makes a statue out of a mountain. Thus, the materiality of memory is realized when geographical elements are inscribed “potentially as documents” (Riceaour, 2009, p. 41). Rightly observes Vohra (2013), the Adi mountains, rivers and lands are “not merely another memory of childhood and youth” of the people but form “part of a continuing relationship with the environment” (p. 46).

The Mnemonic in Tribal Rites and Rituals

In an article on Arunachal Pradesh, Dai argues that Arunachal Pradesh is still one of the “last frontiers of the world” where the indigenous ritual and rites survive almost in uncontaminated forms and the material memory in her poems brings this issue to the fore (Dai, 2009, as cited in Vohra, 2013, p. 47). In “The Voice of the Mountain,” when the Mountain describes how “the other day a young man arrived from the village” with “a gift of fish,” it actually documents the indigenous practices of offering material objects, so typical of the people of the Adi tribe (Dai, 2016). The reference to the “star diagram,” points out the nature of the traditional knowledge of the tribe and how its belief system is intrinsically entwined with nature. So, the tribe’s lifestyle through its materiality replicates the traditional practices

mnemonically. In “Small Towns and the River,” the memory of the dead ones is crystallized in mortuary, material, ritualistic practices. The mourners look at the “sad wreath of tuberoses” that are placed in front of the body while weeping and the body is placed pointing west (Dai, 2012). The placement of the dead in a particular direction is in memory of the timeless cosmic legends of the Adis. As material memory is typically known to do, these “practices of a cultural system...function to ensure memory’s stabilization” (Terdiman, 2018, p. 27) and distance it from an obscure, voiceless past. Halbwachs (2010) in *Les Cadres Sociaux De La Mémoire*, puts forth the argument that memory is a social phenomenon and that remembering occurs in collective contexts. So, the material, ritualistic practices of the Adi in Dai’s poems show how material memory leads to an increased discussion of the ethnic character of the tribe in terms of cultural or collective memory rather than the secular identities of nation and state that the North East hinterlands problematize.

Everydayness of Material Memory

Dai by exploring the materiality of memory reveals its underlying grassroots energy and, thereby, deconstructs the loftiness and magnanimity that are otherwise tied to terms like ‘history’ and the ‘past.’ While foregrounding the day-to-day utility of the material memories, she also brings out the love that the Adis have for their cultural artefacts. In “Small Towns and the River,” Dai talks about the “shrine of happy pictures” that “marks the days of childhood” (2012). One can almost picture the people from the small town that Dai describes, gazing time and again, at the jovial, effervescent moments of their life anchored in polaroids that have survived the bittersweet passage of age and time. Again, in “Floating Island,” Dai describes a woman in sleep who presses her cheek on the pillow “vivid with dreams” (2018). It is as if the pillow in being redolent with reminiscences becomes the token of her memory. In “The Desire of Ink,” the references to usage of ‘boats’ and ‘nets,’ indicate that these props carry mnemonic traces of occupational activities like fishing that have been sustaining the tribal life for aeons (Dai, 2021). Again, in “Once

Upon a 'Time in Pasighat,' the 'unswept' house with bamboo leaves, glows with the warmth that Adi homes are memorable for; where instead of furniture, bits and pieces of nature adorn the floor (Dai, 2021). Thus, all these little things highlight the capillarity of material memory. Their apparently inconsequential nature also creates in them a tendency to escape historical documentation and thereby, again stresses the alterity of material memory. Because of Dai's documentation of the everyday life, a spectacle of the material culture of the Adis sweeps her poetry. And since one needs to come into contact with objects to perceive them empirically, Dai's poems are aesthetic storehouses of visual, verbal, auditory and other sensory images. Thus, the material memory in Dai's poems reveals the desire of the people of her tribe to maintain certain continuities of experience because of which their artefacts become metonyms of the larger culture.

Memory's Structural Character

Some of the memory scholars have also pointed out that the array of physical articles hints at the structuralist character of memory. Terdiman (2018), for instance, claims that memory is much "coincident with representation with the function by which symbols, or simulacra, or surrogates, come to stand for some absent referent" (p. 8). Funkenstein (1993) also creates an analogy between memory and Ferdinand de Saussure's concept of *langue* and *parole*. Thus, according to these scholars, memory too like language is a system of differences. While individual memory or personal memory is the instance of the individual utterance or *parole*, collective memory is the *langue* or the larger language system which backs the former up. But the materiality of memory casts doubts over such a simplistic observation. Material memory, such as, artefacts, monuments, scriptures, comprise signifiers that never float free like a Saussurean signifier but are, rather, grounded. The materiality makes the artefacts both objects and signs and checks any arbitrary relation that otherwise exists in between the signifier and the signified. Thus, the material memory in Dai's poems is as palpable as the 'sign,' the scar that the spear leaves while leaning by the

tree in “The Voice of the Mountain” (Dai, 2016).

Politics and Material Memory

Dai’s poems constantly bring to the fore the political potential of material memory. Terdiman (2018) observes that memory is “inherently contestatory” (p. 20). So, as discussed before, material memory can challenge the official history of the nation-state which is often used as a tool of oppression by the hegemonic masses against minorities. Material history allows exploitation of the alternate ethno-racial histories against infringement of various cosmopolitan discourses and the epistemic violence of modern historiographies and museology. In this context, the Adis, as presented by Dai in her poems, can be called what Nora (1989) labels as peoples of memory. Memory with its subaltern status survives among such people without written, secular histories as an alternative mode. They, in fact, find very little use of modern historiography (which cannot ever replace their oral histories) and have been almost forced to face the facets of modernity. So, Dai in her poems have led the discourses of the Adis’ difference from the mainland exercise a mnemonic task: they ‘recall’ the material lives of the mainland’s Other that was being systematically bleached out. The political concerns of some of the poems are indeed very explicit. In “The Voice of the Mountain,” it is interesting to observe that the poem begins by making the readers realize the Mountain’s (a material memory of the Adis) awareness of its physical distance from the mainland:

I know the towns, the estuary mouth. There, beyond the last bank where the colour drains from heaven I can outline the chapters of the world (Dai, 2016)

In fact, they stress the need for addressing the ‘mainland versus hinterland’ debate in proper contexts on the socio-national imaginary. The “chapters of the world” outlined by this Adi Mountain also reverses the politics of cartography and suggests a map drawn from the fringes, that is again a material which will mnemonically

summon the radical geo-political differences of Dai's land. In "Gone," there are references to guns and gulls "tugging at land and oceans," (line 6) and ropes coiled to "barren rock" (Dai, 2018). These material entities definitely evoke the memories of the bloody history of not only the Adi tribe but most of the other tribes of the North East. Thus, Dai proves that material memory does not exist innocently in vacuum. It, rather, showcases how the "struggles for minority rights are increasingly organized around questions of cultural memory" (Hussey, 1995, p. 5).

Material memory is also yielded as a tool which helps in the sustenance of community values, on the one hand, and, on the other, in the fight against the new cultural as contacts with the mainland grow due to migration of the tribe members. Hussey (1995) calls this the twilight memory or "generational memories on the wane due to the passing of time and the continuing speed of technological modernization" (p. 3). But he also says that in the "last light of the day may still play out its ultimate marvels" as it is "memory's privileged time" (Hussey, 1995, p. 3). Dai definitely lets the material memory in her poems play out its power. In fact, in circumstances when memory struggles to survive, Dai stresses on the warmth of the ancestral and insists on the repetition of traditions by the youth. She wants to wake the youth from their ethnological, mnemonic slumber. In "Once Upon a Time in Pasighat," the materiality of the house that grows old with its "broad roof" from which sunlight peeps in, the "beauty of the bone," and the "universe on the walls," becomes a transgenerational site of memory, the 'timelessness' of which, the children of 'tomorrow' will 'know' (Dai, 2021). But for those who have migrated to cities, away from the tribal small towns, the process of such a remembering is increased as they are far removed from the materiality of memory. In "Gone," the issue of moving away from the apex of tribal life is captured by the lines: "We have long journeys in our blood./The road has no end" and "the horizon burns in my head" (Dai, 2018). The tiredness and discontent of the Adi migrants are clearly manifest in these lines. In such a context, Dai feels that there is only one path to survival and that path is an ecological one. No matter where they are, the

dislocated persons must try to stick to the Adi ethos of maintaining harmony between themselves and nature. Brisking through the urban debris, they will have to conserve the bits and pieces of nature; they will have to commit to their memories the ecological lifestyle of the tribe with the help of material-cultural memory. In *Midsummer Survival Lyrics*, Dai emphasizes, “we cannot crush the mountains or tear off the green covering saying this is what is getting in the way of development. The life of plants and worms and insects is very enduring. We have ample proof of this. So we, too, have to endure” (2014, p. 53). So, the materiality of memory in Dai’s poems show the struggle of the tribal youth who migrate far away, to remain “entwined in the intimacy of a collective heritage,” and not get carried away by the fleeting stream of current affairs (Nora, 1989, p. 8).

Dai’s Poetry as Meta-Memory

Mamang Dai’s act of writing the materiality of memory can itself be perceived as just another material memory as it is the scriptural representation of mnemonics. Thus, the literary technique of conserving memory becomes memory itself. In “The Desire of Ink,” Dai talks about the “the tender scars of/ witness on a page... shaped around a hope” (2021). It is as if she writes self-reflexively about her own body of work that in spite of being scarred by majoritarian infringements, hopes and dreams to pin the authenticity of tribal life and the North Eastern culture on the national map. The conservationist property of these mnemonic objects gets intertwined with her act of writing them down to conserve her tribe’s legends, origins and nature. Dai’s poems, thus, could be seen as meta-memories.

Conclusion

In an age of mechanical reproduction of art, when factories loom large and produce machine-made goods, the story of the origins of the goods, the labour spent behind them gets obscured by an overarching exchange value or their market price. In this age of commodity fetishism, Dai’s deliberate foregrounding of the

artefacts used in daily lives of small villages shows how ethnicity is still prominent in lives that are unwashed by the eddy of hegemonic capitalism. When capitalism veils the memory of production of objects from the consumers, Dai shows how among the Adis almost every object has a story, a legend and a culture lurking beneath its surface.

Dai isolates Adi culture from the modern museum where the archive is canonized and majoritarian values are ossified in the exhibits. Her poetry sets up a parallel exhibition: where material memories of the tribe are galleried; where a mountain becomes a monument and spears and ink fall into the palm of the hands of the person who wants to remember – who needs to remember. Dai shows that beyond spoken “language and the desperation of words,” beyond the abstractness of memories that make the world ‘scallop’ a ‘shell’ of amnesia, are the object-memories that keep on “shooting up like swordfish,” hitting with full force of their materiality (2018; 2021a; 2021b). On the ‘walls’ of her poems, indeed, is hung the entire ‘universe’ of Adi memories (Dai, 2021).

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Colonialism and Resistance: A Gendered Perspective in Select Texts from the Northeast

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Abstract

In a paper titled “Colonialism and Resistance: A Gendered Perspective in Select Texts from the Northeast,” the primary aim is to examine Indira Goswami’s *The Bronze Sword of Thengphakhri Tehsildar* (2013), Mamang Dai’s *The Black Hill* (2014) and Easterine Kire’s *A Respectable Woman* (2019). The paper wishes to explore how each of these three representative women novelists from the northeast narrativise the historical encounter between the British and the indigenous people of Assam, Arunachal Pradesh and Nagaland, and offer a reading of that encounter that challenges the hegemonic mainstream narrative of the freedom struggle. The paper will offer a close reading as well as a comparative study of the three novels using a postcolonial theoretical framework in tandem with a feminist perspective to survey how resistance is often located at the margins not only of gender but also, sometimes, in terms of ethnicities. It would also be of interest to examine during the course of the paper if the resistance offered by the women protagonists is based on a premise of the protecting and nurturing one’s land and its people that is in contrast to the masculinist values of valour and heroism that propel the men to take up arms for resistance, thereby hoping to establish the emphasis on the need for peace that unites these three disparate novels.

Key words: Novels, northeast, colonialism, post-colonialism, narrative, marginalised, historiography, resistance, feminist.

Introduction

Colonialism and Resistance: A Gendered Perspective in Select Texts from the Northeast

The history of the freedom movement can perhaps be seen as a history of several movements across time and space, with people across the gender spectrum, cutting across caste, class, religious and linguistic divides; playing their pivotal role and contributing to the cause of independence from British colonialism. The Indian novel that comes into existence post colonialism, is to a great extent seen as a post-colonial novel due to a variety of reasons. The novel as a genre comes to India as a result of the colonial encounter and invigorates the literary landscape of India. But as Meenakshi Mukherjee writes, the novel that emerges cannot be viewed “as purely a legacy of British rule” (Mukherjee, 1994, p.3). It is interesting to note how the genre is appropriated in a subversive manner to write a narrative of resistance, especially about the colonial encounter and the ideology of imperialism that was used to legitimise its rule. The novel that thus emerges, also, importantly, challenges the supposed passivity of the colonised towards colonialism, and registers the numerous stories of resistance at the macro and micro level in a variety of ways. One of the most interesting developments as far as the novel in post-colonial times is concerned, is the use of English, the coloniser’s language, to write back to the empire as Ashcroft, Griffiths and Tiffin (2002) argue in *The Empire Writes Back*. However, what one increasingly notes is the absence of the northeast - the stories and histories of the impact of British colonialism in the region and its people, their contribution to the freedom struggle, and the far-reaching impact on their political-social-cultural milieu - in both mainstream history of British colonialism in India and the Freedom Movement; or in any discussion of the post-colonial Indian novel. What this paper seeks to achieve, is to position the novel from the northeast as an integral part of the post-colonial Indian novel.

In order to do so, the paper will closely examine Indira Goswami's *The Bronze Sword of Thengphakbri Tehsildar*, Mamang Dai's *The Black Hill* and Easterine Kire's *The Respectable Woman*. Through such an examination, the paper will study how the colonial encounter was of great import to the region, especially keeping in mind its geographical location and proximity to areas such as Burma, a place of strategic importance to the British for purposes of trade and expansion. Further, a perusal of these novels will show how the Second World War, in particular, had a devastating impact on parts of the northeast, an impact that the rest of India was mostly protected from. Also, this colonial encounter and its impact is often presented in terms of the missionary enterprises undertaken by the Empire with motives that surpassed its obvious and fairly successful proselytising mission. This again is well demonstrated by novels such as *The Black Hill*. The paper will ably go on to study how while there is a particular complexity that marks the colonial encounter, with a certain benevolence associated with the colonisers, or even a tendency of the native to mimic the coloniser; the novels also write stories of great resistance to British colonialism that the northeast demonstrated. The paper also aims to examine how the consequences of colonialism impinge on post-colonial policy making, and sometimes further the injustices that were set in motion during colonial times, thereby resulting in resistance to mainstream politics and national agendas in contemporary times. Lastly, the paper will look at how both the impact and resistance to colonialism is often seen through a gendered lens in the novel from the northeast. What is remarkable is that the women who display such resistance are often situated at the very margins of society, thus enabling one to revisit their fight almost as a subaltern one. The paper, in its conclusion will look at if a narrative different from that of chauvinistic nationalism which was seen as catalysing resistance to colonialism thus successfully emerges.

Indira Goswami's *The Bronze Sword of Thengphakbri Tehsildar* was originally published in 2009 and its translation by Aruni Kashyap was published in 2013. Set in nineteenth century Assam, *The Bronze*, the last work of fiction published by

Goswami before her demise, features an unusual protagonist at the centre of the story - a Tehsildar, arguably the first Bodo woman, to serve as a revenue collector in British India. Thengphakhri being a Bodo woman is of special significance as the Bodos comprise the largest ethnolinguistic tribe of Assam, and the novel was published in the year an accord was signed between the Indian government and the outfit responsible for making a demand for a separate state of Bodoland. The novel delineates a period of three years in Thengphakhri's life, from 1857 to 1859, a period that interestingly coincides with the Revolt of 1857 and its aftermath at the national level. The story, set in the kingdom of Bijni, begins with Thengphakhri as a tax collector working for the British, presenting her as a faithful and obedient servant of the British. Right at the onset. The deceptive simplicity of Thengphakhri's description as well as the work she does, leads to some noteworthy surmises. While Thengphakhri is described in a manner wherein her femininity is emphasised upon, the very same is undercut by the fact she is seen as riding a horse. Similarly, her Bodo identity furthered by her choice of wearing the *dokhona*, a garment worn by Bodo women, is complicated by the hat sitting on top of her long, black hair. The image that is therefore put forth, is one marked with confusing complexity, undercutting normative ideas of both gender and identity. As far as Thengphakhri's identity is concerned, an image of hybridity, to borrow a term from Homi Bhabha, is put forward. Such an image becomes interesting to dissect, because, right from the beginning, she is depicted as somebody not only completely loyal to the British but one who evidently tries hard to mimic the British as borne out by her repeated attempts at pronouncing the word "screw-pine" correctly in English at the insistence of her mentor, Hardy.

Our belief in Thengphakhri's allegiance to the British is further strengthened as we witness her bond with Hardy, a man with whom a romantic relationship is hinted at but never articulated. However, as the story progresses, as Thengphakhri bears witness to and is even made to participate in heart-wrenching acts of cruelty to discipline the tax defaulters, people who are not only her own but burdened by

abject poverty, one begins to see a growing tussle in Thengphakhri between the dictates of her heart and her duty as a Tehsildar for the British. The deception of Macklinson and Naken Clark in making Thengphakhri an accessory to the capture of Prince Ramchandra, the rebel leader, becomes the turning point for Thengphakhri, a mental turmoil precipitated by the suspicious circumstances in which her uncle is found dead. Subsequent to this deception, Thengphakhri joins hands with the rebel leaders in their attempt to free Prince Ramchandra from the captivity of the British. However, right from the beginning, it is interesting to note that underlying Thengphakhri's seeming complete allegiance to the British is the possibility of ambiguity. This ambiguity is articulated in Thengphakhri's silence to which the reader's attention is purposefully drawn. This silence has been read as her unquestioning loyalty to the British, but, as Tejoswita Saikia observes, such a reading of silence as acquiescence, or silence as passive acceptance, perhaps arises out of the hegemonic Western discourse that imbues silence with oppression, and voice with agency and empowerment. Lending credence to Saikia's reading is the fact that ambivalence, hybridity has been notably communicated as a space of resistance by Bhabha; and therefore, Thengphakhri's silence can be read as strategic, as a silence that makes possible the creation of the space to articulate dissent; her refusal to capitulate to the British embodied by her continuing to wear the dokhona. For instance, when Macklinson tells Thengphakhri that "It is because of our efforts that you will not smell the burnt flesh of satis but instead you will get the light of Western education," (Goswami, 2013, p. 736) we are told, "She remained completely silent" (Goswami, 2013, p.741).

Mamang Dai's *The Black Hill* was published in 2014 and tells the story of Gimur who belongs to the Abor tribe and marries Kajinsha from the Mishmee tribe, a marriage that alienates her from her people; and how their fate intersects with that of Father Nicolas Krick, a French Jesuit priest, for whose murder Kanjisha is held responsible. The story begins in 1847, exactly a hundred years before India gains independence from the British. The British, who are referred to as Migluns,

are eyed with suspicion right from the beginning of the novel and one is told, “Since the British had occupied Assam, their hills had been disturbed by these strange, foreign men who crept deeper and deeper into their land carrying gifts of salt, iron, tobacco and opium” (Dai, 2014, p.16). What comes across is a sense of the British as unwelcome intruders who upset the balance of things and bring with them all things undesirable. In fact, Gimur is shown as excited by the prospect of a war with the British, displaying no fear for the same and instead proclaiming, “the British were a fearsome race of people ... They travelled up and down the country trying to enter other people’s land without any respect for anyone ... Someone should teach them a lesson” (Dai, 2014, p.24). Apart from a fearlessness, Dai’s novel shows that in a region in which animosity amongst tribes was intense, often resulting in fights over territories and resources, the tribes united to fight against the British, putting aside their own differences. In fact, Dai draws our attention to how these divisions, even within the same tribe, were exploited by the British such as in the instance where “a rift had been created among the Mishmee, with some families willing to aid the white man for salt and money, while others spurned their offers, until open hostility broke out between brothers” (Dai, 2014, pp.112-113). One of the key reasons for highlighting this consciously forged unity, and the resistance it offered was that it was alleged that the Abors had helped the besieged British garrison at Suddya in 1839, an allegation that was true for a small handful of Abors, but one that tarnished the reputation of all of them. The novel, therefore can be seen as an attempt to rewrite the dominant narrative and depict the heroism of the Abors who set aside differences and joined hands with the Khampti warriors and attacked the Suddya garrison in 1839, resulting in the death of Colonel Adam White, the Political Agent, and about eighty of his men.

The other narrative that Dai’s novel seeks to dispel is that of the white man’s burden to civilise the world. One of the first encounters between the British and the Mishmees the novel presents is the one initiated by the British for setting up a trading post a few miles from a river inhabited by the Mishmees, a request undermining all

claims of disinterested benevolence towards the natives. Another revealing incident sheds more light on the hypocrisy of the white man. Father Krick is accompanied on his journey to Tibet by Charles Alexis Renou and it is made abundantly clear that the primary motivation for undertaking the arduous journey was simply to find a route across the Himalaya through India to Tibet. Tillotoma Misra refers to this practice and writes, “the imperial zeal to map, control and possess territories of strategic importance, did not fail to motivate the British ... These expeditions were primarily aimed at discovering alternate trade routes to Tibet and China” (Misra, 2007, p.3655). Renou was of course a part of the Paris Missions but that only further confirms how the white man was united in his imperialist pursuits. Further, at another point, Renoa notes how the whole of Tibet was under the scourge of smallpox, thus providing the perfect opportunity for the missionary to use his knowledge of medicine to endear himself to the indigenous population as “This would pave the way for the spread of the holy gospel” (Dai, 2014, p.42). Of course, as has already been made abundantly clear, the novel elucidates how underlying the proselytising agenda was a more dangerous one of colonising a people and their land for which the help of the locals was deceptively engaged. But while the valour and heroism of the men - Abors, Mishmess, Khamptis, amongst others is validated, a note of despondency, about the futility of wars and violence in the pursuit of land and power, is also strongly struck. Gimur poignantly ponders:

What is land? Men spoke of land as a possession ... Every piece of earth is claimed. The big trees, the high mountains, the rivers rushing down crevasses, the steep cliffs and jagged rocks ... Men fought and killed each other. Blood flowed. Brothers became enemies. How could the mere features of a landscape ignite such love and ferocity. (Dai, 2014, p.72)

The fact that men are propelled to fight wars not just for the love of their land is further reiterated when Kajinsha resolves to inflict “wrath on his enemies ... burn their houses to the ground and take men and women as slaves” (Dai, 2014, p.113) after being taunted by Marpa as he needed to avenge the slur on his father’s name

who was wrongly accused of not joining the Khampti rebellion. It is this anger that fuels Kajinsha's pursuit of power, the price of which is paid by Gimur to a large extent.

Easterine Kire's *A Respectable Woman*, published in 2019, pushes the discussion on postcoloniality of the novel from the northeast, closer to debates in contemporary times. The novel begins with the dramatic statement from the narrator: "It took my mother, Khonuo, exactly forty-five years before she could bring herself to talk about the war. She was ten years old when the Japanese invaded our hills in 1944" (Kire, 2019, p.3). What these lines allude to is a silence that surrounds historical narratives about India under colonialism and its failure to address the impact of the Second World War on the north-east. Several parts of the north-east were bombed during the war and Indian soldiers, including those from the north-east, had enlisted and fought alongside the British during the war which left most of the rest of India, the mainland, untouched. Khonuo's silence thus becomes symbolic of the silence that prevails in the mainstream history of India about this catastrophic event, and also highlights the resultant trauma that perhaps robs the ability for articulation in the victims it left behind. Finally narrating stories from the time of the war, Azuo says, "It was a period of our history that was of great interest to us" (Kire, 2019, p.5). Kire's novel narrates how "young Naga men were running off to join the British army ... because the pay was good and no young man could resist getting a rifle to call his own. There are songs written about these men" (Kire, 2019, 52). Apart from the participation of Naga youth in the war, what these lines also draw attention to is the valour and the heroism that is associated with war, characteristics that are particularly celebrated in men. Interestingly, the women who are left behind in such a scenario draw very different lessons from the war and find entirely different reasons to remember the war, celebrating the generosity and the benevolence that people witnessed in those hard times. As Azuo remarks, "The way the enemy soldiers were scrambling for food and taking away whatever they could get from the villagers was awful to see ... but in the midst of all that, there were widows who went

around to check if everyone in their camp had got food” (Kire, 2019, p.38). Thus, a more compassionate view of the world, even amidst violence, is put forth by the women, indirectly challenging the chauvinistic values endorsed by the men. The novel however presents a relationship with the British that is different from the one usually put forth about the colonisers. What comes across in Kire’s novel is a greater degree of acceptance of the British, to the extent that when the then government’s orders for the missionaries to leave came, the people were shocked as “they had become such a part of our community” (Kire, 2019, p.23). This acceptance of the white man though, did not translate into their being more mindful of local issues and prevalent culture. Kire tells us that a typical white man couldn’t fathom boundaries that depended on topography, where gullies and rock formations marked boundaries between clan lands. As Khonuo and Kevinuo discuss in the novel, this lack of understanding is seen as responsible for the halving of Nagaland between Burma and the British by the British. Unfortunately, this lack of understanding is seen as extending to postcolonial times and Kire’s novel also launches a scathing attack on the apathy that meets the region and its people. The rampant problem of alcoholism that the novel deals with is blamed on “the political situation, the brutality of army occupation, the transition from rural to modern which left some people out in the cold because they did not have enough education or skills ...” (Kire, 2019, p.133). These accusations, especially given Nagaland’s troubled relationship with India, for being made a part of it, throw a huge challenge to the idea of India as a nation and fractures a notion of a homogenous, uncontested nationalism. R. Bhumika makes an incisive statement observing how “This simultaneity of inhabiting both ‘postnational’ and nationalist space while also exhibiting features of postcolonial literary text, needs to be read as an important aspect of Naga literature in English” (Bhumika, 2019, p.584).

The paper has so far undertaken a close reading of the three novels to understand and assign a stance of postcoloniality to these novels. Further, what needs to be explored and reiterated is a sense that such postcoloniality is a collective

stance underlying many novels from various parts of the northeast, irrespective of whether there is a conscious or subconscious strategy at work to establish them as such. In fact, if one looks at the novels written in English, or translated into English; a certain politics of positioning the literature and its people against both colonial and postcolonial constructions of what the northeast seemingly represents, or how it has been represented not just in history, literature but also popular culture, is effectively interrogated. The idea of benevolent colonialism is repeatedly questioned in the novels examined. *The Bronze Sword of Thengphakbri Tehsildar* subversively locates a space of resistance even when seemingly its protagonist appears to surrender to the alleged superiority of the coloniser by adopting strategic hybridity. As Bhabha says “Hybridity is a problematic of colonial representation and individuation that reverses the effects of colonialist disavowal, so that the other ‘denied’ knowledges enter upon the dominant discourse and estrange the basis of its authority” (Bhabha, 1994, p.114). Such a subversive dismantling of authority is effectively illustrated in *The Bronze Sword of Thengphakbri Tehsildar*. Similarly, postcoloniality by Dai is affirmed by rewriting a story of betrayal as one of not just resistance by the Abors and Mishmees but in doing so unravelling the lies of the white man’s narrative of civilising the world. Kire’s *A Respectable Woman* not only fills in the gaps of mainstream history but can be seen as postcolonial even in its narrativising strategy. As Gaur and Sarkar note, Kire’s “use of oral tales foregrounds a tradition of writing that indigenises the western forms to suit the cultural imagination of Naga people” (Gaur and Sarkar, 2021, p.933). Further, Gaur and Sarkar comments on how Kire “develops a memoryfictional narrative technique” (Gaur and Sarkar, 2021, p.937) to represent in fiction memories collated from survivors to write history.

Tanja E Bosch (2016) notes how foundational theorists of Memory Studies such as Maurice Halbwachs look at the concept of memory as destabilising grand narratives of history and power. Such a use of memory, wherein individual or collective memories of a social group are privileged by subordinating prevalent narratives, is just one of the many strategies that one observes the writer from the

northeast adopting to use the Western genre of the novel to achieve their own desired goal. Referring to the privileging of memory that one notices even in Mamang Dai's novels, Papiya Ghosh (2019) states that writing orality is a characteristic of literature from the north-east. The truth of Ghosh's perceptive remark is borne out by the fact that Goswami's story of Thengphakhri is collated from folk songs and folk tales celebrating her life and not from any written historical archive. There is often an element of storytelling that is woven into the very narrative of the novel, such as Khonuo telling the stories of the Second World War to her daughter, that highlight the rich oral tradition prevalent in the northeast. Such strategies not only subvert the use of the Western genre of the novel but also the adverse impact that the rise of print-capitalism had in this region, catalysed by the setting up of the printing press in Sibsagar by the American Baptist Mission and the translation and the dissemination of the Bible. These strategies are necessary to be pointed out because much of the writing from the northeast, including two of the novels discussed in this paper, are novels written in English, the language that became a part of Indian languages as a consequence of colonialism. As Tilottoma Misra points out, English becomes the inevitable choice of some of these writers, thereby, ironically creating a "distance from the native speaker of the region they come from" (Misra, 2007, p.3653) not only as a result of colonial language policies but also post-colonial policy decisions. Most states of the northeast are linguistically very diverse and in the absence of a script or a lack of a viable audience resulting from how small these linguistic communities may be, the choice of English becomes the only practical one. But by effectively using elements of orality, foregrounding memory, using folklore, amongst other things, to posit stories of resistance, the novel from the northeast emerges as a truly postcolonial one. What sets the novel from the northeast apart from the postcolonial novel from the rest of India is how its interrogation goes beyond colonial politics to critique contemporary politics and political agendas. Also, given the continuing presence of violence in the northeast from both state and non-state actors, a constant advocacy for peace, a downplaying of masculinist-

nationalism becomes a defining characteristic of the novel from the northeast, and one that sets it apart. This promotion and validation of peace may owe its inception to Gandhian politics of non-violence, but it is also located in the immediate concerns of preserving one's culture and tradition, as well as a deep veneration for the environment, which makes it suspicious of the coloniser as well as a chauvinistic practice of nationalism. Dismayed at the felling of trees to create a playground for the British soldiers to practise horse-riding, Thengphakhri regrets how "Several gondhoxrai, yellow myrobalan and phoolsompa trees had to be destroyed in the process" (Goswami, 2013, p.305). It is this concern beyond land and power, concern for the people and the forests and the trees, that seem to be the driving force behind the resistance displayed by the women in the novels explored. What these novels from the northeast delve into is what Alfred Crosby terms ecological imperialism which Huggan and Tiffin state "ranges in implication and intensity from the violent appropriation of indigenous land to the ill-considered introduction of non-domestic livestock and European agricultural practices" (Huggan and Tiffin, 2015, p.3). In the postcoloniality of the novel from the northeast, thus one can locate not just resistance but also find embedded within it, a nascent concern for a posthuman world voiced by the concern of these women writers and their protagonists, which then charts a new direction for the novel in India.

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Indigenous Aesthetics and Nature in Mizo Myths

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Abstract:

A collection of Mizo Folktales from the Tribe of Mizos, *The mizo Myths* (2015) was authored by Cherrie Lalnunziri Chhange. The focus of these Folktales gives a narrative. It has been said that presumably simple tales are embedded in folks' attitudes regarding social structures, gender relations, mystical conviction and methods, relationship with nature, and survival strategies. Justifying our beliefs and intellectualizing and analyzing the approval in its central to folk epistemology. The Indigenous Aesthetic elements, such as songs, mythical and the ridiculous all come together to form a unique fabric eccentric narrative arrangement that are unlike any other "modern" plot-and paradoxically uses the same archetypes found so much in today's literature of any genre. Through this, the paper will apprise the Mizo Myth with the help of four myth theories namely Rational Myth, Functional Myth, Structural Myth and Psychological Myth illustrated by Bronislaw Malinowski, C.G. Jung and Freud, Claude Lévi-Strauss and Deep Ecology under ecocriticism by Arne Naess with some other sub-genre, like fantasy, fairytale of folklore.

Keywords: Myths theories, Fantasy, Mizo Folktales, Romanticism

INTRODUCTION

Indigenous Aesthetics which falls under the northeast region of Mizo folklores is an important literature written by the genuine native writers to preserve the historical tales of the Mizo tribes as the tales are profoundly attach to the soil that represent their identity. The book, *Mizo Myths* comprises of different tales such as

Tumchhngi and Raldawna, Chawngtinleri, The Tale of the Beginning of the World the Creation of The Earth, The Swallowing of the Moon, Thimzing, The Great Darkness, Chhinlung, The Feast of Thlanrawkpa, The Naming of the Animal, The Bamboo Rat and The Drum, The Loris and The Sun, The Tortoise and The Python's Eggs, The Great War of Animals. The above tales will be the essentials for the project using *myth theories* by Bronislaw Malinowski, C.G. Jung and Freud, Claude Lévi-Strauss.

Like many of my fellow epistemologists, I think that reflection on knowledge ascription can contribute to our understanding of the nature of knowledge ascriptions can contribute to our understanding of the nature of knowledge as well as to the semantics of 'knowledge'. (Gerken, 2017, p. 07)

The word myth has its origin from Ancient Greek "mythos", meaning 'speech, narrative, fiction, myth and plot'. A myth is supernatural elements that have been told time and time again with different phase. It illustrates the indigenous roots about the nature, history and tangible conditions of the world, human being and society. Varieties of theories are in fact relevant while some has exceptional explanation with different thing about myth. In the concept of the tale from Tumchhngi and Raldawna and the tale of Chawngtinleri is relevant in the theory of functional myths, structural myths, and psychological myth.

As the term of psychological myth given by "The psychological myth theory explains that myths are related with human emotion and appear from the human subconscious" (Rani, 2015, p. 442). Giving an illustration of psychological myth from the tale of Tumchhngi and Raldawna it is relevant that he (Raldawna) stumbles upon the nightshade plant with beautiful bright red berries while clearing the jhum field along with his mother. This sight led Raldawna to question if there was a maiden as beautiful as the berries. The lines, "Mother, do you think it's possible that there is a girl somewhere who is as beautiful as this fruit?" asked Raldawna" (Chhangte, 2016, p. 16). This was the inceptive state of Raldawna's subconscious to

be directed towards the pursuit of a lady, that attributes to the psychological theory that Jung talks about.

The appearance of the goblin phungpuinu (a very ugly female goblin) “who caught sight of Tunchingi’s shadow on the ground” (17) was unconsciously amazed by her beautiful shadow which implies that she is clouded by her disillusionment. Where phungpuinu sang.

“I myself wear no ornaments, but look!
My shadow wears bangles, jingle jangle,
My shadow wears necklaces, jingle jangle” (18).

Jung advocated further that, “The ego comprises the conscious mind, the personal unconscious comprises once conscious material that has been suppressed due to its social inappropriateness” (Dawroski, 2016, 07). As Jung contemplate individuals and attempt to comprehend how components of the conscious and unconscious interact to create personality.

Looking from our current ‘computer age’ perspective, we could perhaps say that the Mizo folks at that point of time were not sufficiently equipped with the logic of scientific intuitions and tend to possess less rational approaches to things beyond their crude existence. We are also aware of their superstitious nature and lack of vibrant cognitive thinking. Yet, after taking all these attributes into considerations, still, we cannot help but wonder and ask whether these minded folks had actually encountered “something” or some force which are utterly different from their normal existence. (Ramdinsangi, 2014, p. 38)

The verbal form such as (stories, poetry, riddles, proverbs, saying) can be the folklore expression, and they express through yelling, singing. Folklore is not obligation to be pass down orally but also through the convention of paintings, visuals, activities, art and belief. Subsequently, with the theory by Bronislaw Malinowski of Functional theory, it explains that enlightening morality is one of the functional myths theories

that is often used in the society and the society itself emphasize to the social guide. In the Story of Chawngtinleri who is known to be the fairies in the village of Seipui, caught an attention who goes by the name Lalchungnunga Lasi (Lasi which means Fairy in Mizo folktales), and the king of tan of the highest hill in Mizoram. The tale will show us how the powers of a man having a Title called Pasalthra and from the example of Chawngtinleri's brother Liana who is blinded by the will to have the power to hunt and was tempted to give away his only sister as a bride-price to earn the title of a powerful warrior who could kill the most fearsome beast of the jungle. Because the lasi kept appearing in his dream several times, he subconsciously agreed to give her sister to the king of Lasi to marry him. From the understanding of Marie-Catherine Le Jumel de barneville, Baroness d'Aulnoy, also known as countess d'Aulnoy, was a French author for her literary *contes de fées* (fairytale). The term is now generally use as a genre, "D'Aulnoy projects the necessity for women to decide their own destiny, but it is a destiny that calls for women to submit themselves to Patriarchal code that is not really of their making". (Zipes, 2021, p. 01)

The tale also reflect on the value system of the people when the faries tempted Lianchea with the rich reward, the reward was in the form of 'gayals' and 'mithuns' which were considered the most priceless possessions at that time. The fairies knew Lianchea so well that they enticed him with his deepest desires; the fulfillment of that desire compels Lianchea to submit to the fairies wishes. (Ramdinsangi, 2014, p. 43)

One must be gratified in terms of what one has and not be tempted by the assets of others. Solely from this, through the tale, what can be perceived is that there are always consequences for something in return and that is the moral of the effect to the point where Lianchea seems to regret his decisions.

He became filled with remorse at having given in to the Lasi. He tries to comfort himself by saying, "it wasn't real! It was just a dream!" still, he didn't dare to tell anyone. (Chhangte, 2016, p. 44)

With references to Freud's Interpretation of Dreams, he wrote how dreams are "disguised fulfillments of repressed wishes" (01), Lianchea seen to have a desired longing for his sister's presence while hunting with his friends on the Tan Hill:

Liana wandered off the paths to explore all the ravines and crevices of hill, hoping to catch sight of Chawngtinleri, but he found no sign of her. Finally, disheartened, he gave up his search and sat on top of a rock. He took a leaf and played it (the art of making music with a leaf was popular in those days) and he started singing:

While I wander lonely and despairing,
how do you pass your days,
My soulmate, my beloved chawngi? (45)

The definition of 'Deep Ecology' given by the Norwegian philosopher Arne Naess in 1972, states that "it can be defined as a social movement aimed toward a philosophical shift, namely that humans should stop viewing nature as a resource and begin to view it as something with inherent value" (Amendolare, 2022, p. 01). Deep ecology also argues that every living creature including animals, plants deserve to be protected and preserved. Examining from the myth *The Story of the Beginning of the world* which consist ten sub-stories mainly 'The Great War of Animals', 'The Tortoise and the Python's Eggs', 'The Loris and the Sun', 'The Bamboo Rat and the Dream', 'The Naming of the the Animals', 'The Feast of Thlanrawkpa', 'Chhinlung', 'Thimzing, the Great Darkness', 'The Swallowing of the Moon', 'The Creation of the Earth', and the concept of deep ecology is interpreted in it.

Fantasy

In the story of the of "The swallowing of the moon", the tale discusses the techniques of fantasy where King Hauhaulh swallows the moon in his dream, which became the outcome of the reality in the waking world. It is also believed that in "Thimzing, the great Darkness" tale, after the death of King Hauhaulh,

he was departed to Pialral (also known as heaven in Mizo) and transformed into Awk creature who have the ability to swallow the sun that could turn the earth into eclipses. Furthermore, it was also during the time in Thimzing, the great darkness where an uncanny encounter takes place, where the process of metamorphosis can be observed by the unexpected transformation that occur. “Some human became monkeys, while others became gibbons, some of the young boys and girls were transformed into karo birds (white-crested laughing thrushes as they are called in English)”. (Chhangte, 2016, p. 24)

Named Khuanzingnu, a goddess, the creator of the earth and all kinds of living beings, she would unlock the gateway of heaven and pour water upon the ground to strengthen the vegetations, in the tale, parallelism can be seen in the ancient Greek Myth, the Japanese Myth and the *Mizo Myth*, where goddess ‘Khuanzingnu’, goddess Izanami, who also possess the power to “create land, trees, islands, and other gods.” “The shintō mother goddess or progenitor Japanese goddess of the country and *kami*. After she dies, she has the power to bring death to humans and the ability to command numerous underworld *kami*” (*kami* the word for deity, divinity or spirit) (Kamiya, n.d., p. 01), and the Greek goddess ‘Gaia’ to be the mother nature of earth: “Gaia was the Greek goddess of Earth, mother of all life, similar to the Roman Terra Mater (mother Earth) reclining with a cornucopia, or the Andean Pachamama, the Hindu, Prithvi, “the Vast One,” or the Hopi Kokyangwuti, Spider Grandmother, who with Sun god Tawa created Earth and its creatures”. (Weyler, 2019, p. 01)

By fantasy I mean the deliberate departure from the limits of what is usually accepted as real and normal. The works covered range from the trivial escapes of pastoral and adventure stories to the religious visions of Langland and Dante. This does not mean that I am trying to relabel all western masterpieces “fantasy”, but fantasy *is an element* in nearly all kinds of literature, especially the narratives, the most important exceptions being realistic novels and some satiric and picaresque works. (Hume, 2014, p. xii)

According to the myth written by Cherrie Lalnunziri, a goddess named Khuazingunu is believed to be the creator of the earth, who one day got very distressed seeing her created beings getting lesser with the feeling of precariousness, “she decided to take couple from each human clan, as well as a representative couple of each animal species, and place them inside a deep cave” (Chhangte, 2016, p. 24). The majority of the mizo clans are said to have originated from a myth in which the original creator of earth at that time decided to make a couple after noticing their loneliness and then decided to produce more humans after sensing their misery. “After four or five generations had been born inside the cave” (24), the goddess Khuazingnu at long last lifted the Chhinlung, like a ‘termites’ outpoured from the rock the ‘great multitudes’ from then, each and every clan emerged: the Lushai, the Chawte, the Pantu, the Ngente and multiple other clans.

With regard to the given tale, the theory of The Rational myth is significant.

Myths are produced to enlighten natural actions and forces that happen in everyday life; Along with it also says that gods and goddesses controlled all of these activities of nature. Creation myth from different cultures are all examples of rational myths. (Rani, 2015, p. 441)

Deep ecology, on the contrary, explains how nature must be protected as Arne Naess elucidated on the movement where he instructed followers to “not only protect the planet for the sake of humans, but also, for the sake of the planet itself”. (Amendolare, 2022, p. 01)

Deep ecology includes not only ecological aspects but also spiritual and ethical ones. It encourages a feeling of ecological self in which people believe they are part of larger cycle of life rather than something apart from it and acknowledges the independence of all life. This point of view promotes reverence for, respect for, and responsibility for the natural environment.

Romanticism and environmental imagination

The Romantic movement was greatly influenced by Schelling's philosophical theories, notably in connection to conception of nature, art and the philosophy of identity. In contrast to the rigid separation between the subjective and objective realms, Schelling's theory emphasized the connection of nature and spirit. In his view, nature and spirit were not two distinct things but rather various outward representations of the same underlying truth.

"Romanticism began in 1805, taking the place of classicism (1786-1805,) and ended around 1835 in Europe. Romanticism influenced the rediscovery of history and the German past; it promoted art, music, literature, folklore, and poetry as the paths of discovery" (Schelling, n.d., p. 01). In the story of Tualvungi (wife) and Zawlpala (husband), we get to see the married couple who are both profoundly in love, in fact, both the couple did have outstanding visuals, nonetheless, the couple have to cut off ties because of the husband's idiocy where a rich Vai (names that are given to people who reside in the plain area of land), an exporter who goes by the name Phuntiha asked if he could marry Tualvungi:

When Phuntiha espied Tualvungi, he thought she was very beautiful indeed.

He asked Zawlpala, "Is that your wife?"

Now, Zawlpala, who was very proud of his wife's beauty, answered in jest, "No, she is my sister."

"Well then," said the haughty phuntiha, "I will make her my wife. In return, what will you demand as bride-price? (Chhangte, 2016, p. 35)

Absurdism can be observed as the tale proceeds, Zawlpala who is unaware of Phuntiha's wealth will soon be impotent, because of the sloppiness jest he made. Tualvungi uttered in "trepidation":

There in the distance, far in the horizon,
He comes leading a great herd of bison,

Burdened with loads of woven cloths;
Say, 'She is with child',
My beloved Zawlpala. (36)

In relation to Pastoral ideology, transmutation takes place within the tale where the couple at last pass away, to which they 'turned themselves' into butterflies; Phunthiha who in pursuit of Tualvungi killed himself and laid beside the lovers and he too turned himself into butterfly.

Historically, pastoral have sometimes activated green consciousness, sometimes euphemized land appropriation. It may direct us toward the realm of physical nature, or it may abstract us from it. This I take to be basic issues of ideology and representation posed by pastoral traditions. (Buell, 1995, p. 31)

The reason to why we frequently spot a twosome butterfly always accompanied by a third butterfly, therefore, till date the Mizos assume the tale to be the reason for that. An example can also be pointed out in Shakespeare's play to the same degree of tragedy, jealousy and idiotic along with moral less story of Tualvungi and Zawlpala. And in the story of Chawngmawii and Hrangchuana in Shakespeare's tragic play is relevant taking "Othello" as a primary illustration who, without the second thought, killed his wife out of jealousy in a similar situation with Zawlpala who, also without the second thought, made a jest without thinking of the consequences. The end of the tale of Tualvungi and Zawlpala fails to deliver the moral and so it can also be considered a moral less tale which instantaneously ended with the dead where the two protagonist and the one antagonist turned into butterflies. Equivalent to the story of Chawngmawii and Hrangchuana, in spite of the fact that it was only the lovers who was executed in an inexcusable manner, in 'Hamlet' both Ophelia and Hamlet died which efficiently takes the place of the intricate interior worlds of the characters they attempt to put forward to existence.

However, it does not necessarily mean that “some ‘literary’ qualities of a Shakespeare text might be lost in performance” (Allen, n. d. p. 01), or incompetent.

For Lamb, and for many of the scholars who have written in this tradition, what differentiates Shakespeare from other early modern playwrights is twofold: for one thing, *he simply is too good*; and for another, his plays contain an (always very hazily defined) ethereal, almost supernatural wisdom that escapes the powers of mere actor to convey (01).

Amidst the catastrophe of the environmental imagination, contrarily finding to understand the relation between human and nature. The challenges Lawrence Buell takes up in *The Environmental Imagination* is that, “it has led me into broad study on environmental perception, and the consequences for literary scholarship and indeed for humanistic thought in general of attempting to imagine a more “ecocentric” way of being”. (Buell, 1995, p. 01)

Enunciating from the story of Tumchhingi and Raldawna, where the goblin swallowed Tumchhingi which has transformed into seed is quite expedient as

She brought up what was left of Tumchhingi, which was just a tiny seed. Soon the seed germinated, and before many days has passed it grew into a large bottle-gourd vine. But the plant only bore a single fruit, which grew very high up on the vine, higher than any passer-by could reach. (Chhange, 2016, p. 20)

Juxtaposing the idea with “The Tale of the Bamboo Cutter and The Moon Child”, by Yei Theodora Ozaki, who usually go out in the morning for cutting bamboos had found a mysterious with a delightful lump of bamboo.

The old man, full of wander, dropped his ax and went towards the light. On nearer approach he saw that this soft splendor came from a hollow in the green bamboo stem, and still more wonderful to behold, in the midst of the brilliance stood a tiny human being, only three inches in height, and exquisitely beautiful in appearance. (Ozaki, 1908, p. 01)

The correlation that can be comparatively put in the tale of “Tumchhingi and Raldawna” when phungpuinu spat out a tiny seed where Tumchhingi resuscitate from the seeds, in contrast to “The Tale of Bamboo Cutter and The Moon Child” where the Princess Moonlight who was unnaturally found inside the bamboo by the bamboo cutter. Considering how ‘Romanticism’ was about bringing light and understanding emotions rather than using them, the element can be seen from this likeness between the two-above tales.

Conclusion

Just as in our own human societies, fairy folk- both good and bad- have their own customs and etiquette too!

-Jade Westerman (Between Worlds, 2018)

The reason as to why man created myth seems to enumerate for exceptionally a few reasons, throughout history, and it has been the main source of storytelling in olden days where elders would speak of natural events, of human nature and of mind, myth like storytelling have been told to children using Oral Verbal. And it was also part of education and have been frequently orchestrate, many of us know there are innumerable stories like, “The Green Knight”, the Princess and the Frog, does comprehend a child-friendly tale, conversely there are displeasing too like the tale of “Snow White” and many more which we have heard from foreign countries. So, when we talk about Mizo folktale, it is mostly unbelievable to the terms how they have come up with such narrative’s ideas of supernatural elements. It has also been understood to that context of Plato and Aristotle’s who asserts that the sense of literature as an imitation, in contradictory to every writer. In spite of the fact that the tales have been rendered orally by the following generation it can be discerned through Chhangte’s exponents as to how

A close reading of the Mizo folktales reveals that, the tales were conspicuously of sometimes subtly permeated by the occurrence of some forms of higher beings or experience which were obviously foreign to themselves and their

simple social environment. (Chhangte, 2016, p. 01)

Buell also examines the idea of “place-consciousness,” which is connected to the imagination of the surroundings. Place-consciousness is the ability to identify the distinctive ecological, historical, and cultural features of a certain location. Understanding how people and their environment are shaped by our surroundings, necessary for this. Despite the fact that the environmental imagination is a nature and a factor in the developing of American culture, by merely mentioning a few instances of this ideas, as Buell’s look at the writings by various American authors, notably Henry David Thoreau, who is regarded as a pivotal figure in the growth of ecological consciousness. He examines how Thoreau’s writings such as “Walden” and his observation of nature, not only describe the natural world but also entice readers to consider their own interactions with it and the effects of contemporary industrial culture of environment. By emphasizing the significance of storytelling and artistic expression in fostering developing a more moral and sustainable connection with the environment.

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Indigenous Epistemology and Aesthetics through Romantic Ecology and Hyperreality in Easterine Kire's *When The River Sleeps* (2014)

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Abstract

Heavily embedded with wisdom and enthralling scenes of the indigenous richness of the habitats of the Angami-Nagas, Easterine Kire's *When The River Sleeps* (2014) is a tale that harmonizes the realities of the physical world with the supernatural. The novel is enchanted with the spellbinding melodies in the narratives that transports the readers right to the mountains of Nagaland situated at the north-eastern part of India. Winner of The Hindu Prize for Fiction in 2015 and known to be a distinguished work of art that brilliantly captures the indigenous aesthetics of the North-East of India, the plot, in its contemporary sense of time frame, runs akin to a world that is undefiled by the presence of the inordinate technology (a pre-digital era, that rejects the utilitarian approach).

What is interesting to note is the effect of how the novel does not necessarily aim to narrate a mere tale of a man who undertakes a journey of adventure to procure the 'magical stone' at the 'sleeping river' and his experiences. It is an anecdote of a sensational expedition that is an amalgamation of the parallels of magic and reality, where spirits share an equivalent space. The indigenous epistemology and aesthetics through the theoretical framework of Romantic Ecology by Johnathan Bates and Hyperreality by Jean Baudrillard, will be studied in the paper to understand how important and powerful indigenous philosophies are to all aesthetic systems.

Keywords: Indigenous Epistemology, Traditional Aesthetics, Romantic Ecology, Hyperreality, Animism

Introduction

“When we see, we are not just looking – we are reading the language of images.”

John Berger (*Ways of Seeing*, 1972)

A winner of the 2015 Hindu Prize for Fiction, which had been known to be a distinguished and exceptional work of art, with “high-fantasy stuff, something out of an Ursula Le Guin novel” (Sarma, 2016, p. 01), *When The River Sleeps* (2014) by Easterine Kire is heavily embedded with wisdom and enthralling scenes of the indigenous richness of the habitats of the Angami-Nagas. Kire is able to produce how “the exoticism has been rendered redundant through his (Vilie’s) parable that exhibits the strong symbiotic relationship between man and nature and the balance between superstition and rationality” (Satapathy, 2020, p. 01), as a connoisseur of contemporary narrative. It is a tale that harmonizes the realities of the physical world with the supernatural and produces an equilibrium between the two.

Incorporated with the webs of fascinating supernatural elements and the marriage with the ecosystem, “Easterine Kire, pens our deep connection with nature for the national readership to gawk at.” (Paul, 2019, p. 01). In its contemporary sense of time frame, the story runs akin to world that is undefiled by the presence of the inordinate technology (a pre-digital era, that rejects the utilitarian approach) where “Kire’s English and her narrative choices harks back to the oral tradition, thus rejecting the western model of the Great Indian Novel, which hinges on the use of language, and sprawling themes” (Sarma, 2016, p. 01) with parallels of magic and reality, where spirits an equivalent space.

What is interesting to note is the effect of how the novel does not necessarily aim to narrate a mere tale of a man who undertakes a journey of adventure to procure the ‘magical stone’ at the ‘sleeping river’ and his experiences. It is an anecdote of a

sensational expedition that is an amalgamation of the “inexplicable natural world that hovers at the edge of human existence, where wisdom extracts its costs” (01) where “evil and unknown spirits, cruel people, beasts lurking amidst the forest etc. and so on” (Hazarika, 2017, p. 598) is dominated by the picturesque journey which included.

Romantic Ecology

In the understanding of Romantic Ecology which was first coined by Jonathan Bates in 1991 in his book by the same name, examines the ways in which writer and thinkers respond to and participate in the history of ecological discipline, environmental ethos and environmental dogmatism. Owing to the study of ecocriticism theory which studies the relationship between literature and environment in general, “it may be quickly added that modern idea of nature and concern for the non-human world, has assumed momentous propensity in environmental criticism in recent times.” (Das, 2009, p. 02). As established by Cheryll Glotfelty in *The Ecocriticism Reader* (1992) “simply defined, ecocriticism is the study of the relationship between literature and the physical environment” (Glotfelty, 1992, p. xix), this very ‘relationship’ and connection to nature is evident in the book where Vilie is observed to be addressing the ‘forest’ as his ‘wife’:

“The forest is my wife, and perhaps this is what marriage is like; with periods when a chasm of loneliness separates the partners leaving each one alone with their own thoughts, groping for answers.” he thought. (Kire, 2014, p. 09)

The union of romanticism and ecology is very relevant in this approach. As understood according to William Wordsworth, nature is the mirror of the presence of God. This sanctity and devoutness that he expounded upon possessed that “nature could be vital restorative power to all who have suffered a breakdown of their faith” (Lacey, 1948, p. 58). From this light, the expedition into the discipline of Romantic

Ecology which stands for the pursuit or yearning for parabolic representations in nature that restore those of religion in terms of vital conglomerate like identity, is efficacious in alliance of one's identity and comprehensive meaning in association to indigenous religion.

The dichotomy of nature and culture is conspicuous in the novel where we can take a trip into the consciousness of Vilie towards Krishna the Nepali woodcutter.

What could school possibly teach him that his parents could not improve upon? They were rich in their knowledge of the ways of the forest, the ways of the forest, the herds one could use for food, the animals and birds one could trap and the bitter herbs to counteract the sting of a poisonous snake. (Kire, 2014, p. 15)

In this understanding, the 'school' of nature metaphorically symbolize 'culture'. The Romantic Ecology here is detectable due to the nature in which it confers itself, since it is done as a process to pressuring a wrecked society keen on taking advantage of natural recourse for indemnification. In this understanding, Wordsworth expounds on how "it would be ideal to revert back to simpler times where nature was held in high regard and was identified as the physical manifestations of god's creations" (Bulman, 2016, p. 01). Thus, "there are resonances of the traditional story telling technique and that is what sets this novella apart" where it is able to haul "to the fore how man and nature can coexist harmoniously even in a capitalist and consumerist driven 21st century". (Satapathy, 2020, p. 01)

In *Romantic Ecology: Wordsworth and the Environmental Tradition* (1991), Johnathan Bate argues how "romantic ideology is not a theory of imagination and symbol, but a theory of ecosystems and alienated labour" (Bate, 1991, p. 10). This shows us how he explores the relationship and distinction between "nature" and "culture", "and seeks the combination of them in "a complex and delicate web"" (Mei, 2007, p. 01). Bate reprehends and uncovers the aesthetics of the picturesque deeply. "If the deeply-rooted anthropocentrism hidden in it cannot be overcome, the ecological

crisis will not reverse, or even further deteriorate” (01). Textual evidence from the novel significantly shows the essence of the argument of Bate, “be very patient my son,” the seer had said. “Only the patient-hearted are granted the blessing of catching the sleeping river”. (Kire, 2014, p. 31)

The approach of Romantic Ecology is explored by Bate with the relationship of culture and nature from the outlook of weather and poetry.

Weather is the primary sign of mutability of nature and the primary sign of entanglement between culture and nature. Humans should read the signs of the times in the signs of the skies. Bate profoundly studies the meaning of “nature”, and reads a wide range of English Romantic works, many of which recovered from underserved obscurity. (Mei, 2007, p. 01)

The appreciation of the nature from the perspective of weather and poetry in *When The River Sleeps*, can be identified by the compliments of the elements where Kire writes about the captivating expanse of the forest that Vilie ventures into which is unbeknownst to him as a mystical expedition to fulfil his dream albeit vicariously. This journey that transforms Vilie spiritually and intellectually and the balances out “the realities of the tangible world with the fantastical of the supernatural”. (Satapathy, 2020, p. 01)

Although the solicitude of an escalating mechanical discretion along with the consciousness of environmental deterioration were observed in the literary texts, ‘Romantic Ecology’ in fact, “assumed a new sense of urgency in the hands of the English Romantics who highlighted the urgency in the hands of the English Romantics who highlighted the question of nature’s ecological fragility and, more importantly, the need of looking into man’s environmental practices” (Das, 2009, p. 02). It is articulated in the criticism of Bate which based on ecological ideas but also incorporates the elements of ‘history’. “He believes that a good criticism should have historical as well as contemporary relevance”. (Madhulika, 2016, p. 13)

As Romantic Ecology takes its stand on the blend on the historical relevances, one can observe how Kire's novel has an intricate flux to the idea of it. This is evident where Vilie can be seen making use of the traditional remedy to help control the bleeding that was grazed from the bullet of Hiesa while escaping from the hands of him.

...he looked around to see if there were any herbs. Finding a patch of *Vilhuu nba*, he made a paste out of the leaves and stuck it on his injury and let the brown juice seep into his open skin the bleeding stopped immediately. (Kire, 2014, p. 49)

Another instance from the text that hints the Romantic Ecological factor is narrated in the seventh chapter titled *The Nettle Forest*, where Kire touches upon the handicraft of Barkweaving by the barkweavers.

The females were harvesting nettle which they would strip for fibre to make into yarn – it was called barkweaving (Kire, 2014. p. 32) . . . they had pared down the stems removing the thorns along the stems. That was what they essentially needed, the long and hard, fibrous stems which they would strip lengthwise and lay in a room for a few days until the bark-fibre was ready to be wound into yarn. Barkweaving was a dying art and it pleased him to see the women diligently harvesting the nettle plants into their baskets. (33)

Romantic ecology is evident here as Wordsworth aims to accomplish the change the notion of 'improvement' in nature referred to in relation with "the tending of land to bring in profit" (Mason, 2010, p. 27). To the likes other ecocritical readings like the classic work of American romanticism and the transcendentalist movement *Walden* by Henry David Thoreau, in which he meticulously records his experiences and the philosophical denotations of his probe to find a more substantial existence in the world, "seeking solitude, self-sufficiency, and harmony in the woods of Concord, Massachusetts". (Aravec, 2104, p. 01)

Ecological critics like Jonathan Bate, Karl Kroeber, James C. McKusick opined that there is an intricate relationship between nature and man that is an unadulterated sensibility. Pursuing parallel line of thoughts amongst themselves, they suggest that the “tension between historicist and ecocritical approaches to the period can be resolved by a re-examination of the origins of ecological thinking generally and Romantic ecology specifically” (Lussier, 2000, p. 192). Bate and McKusick both deliberately points out to John Clare (also known as the “Northamptonshire Peasant”), as the elaborator of “ecopoiesis”. “Clare reflects “the ontology of the poetic” identified by Bachelard, and the resulting poetry expresses a constant “topophilia,” a love of place” (195). The acute sense of belonging to the forest and the geographical penetration within the story is colossal, wherein Vilie is seen in conversation with one of the women in the chapter titled The Border Village

“This is our home, do you understand? We cannot abandon it and try to live in another place. Our umbilical cords are buried here, and we would always be restless if we tried to settle elsewhere.” Subale explained. (Kire 2014, p. 88)

From this prospect, Kire draws upon the place attachment in *When The River Sleeps* time and time again.

Hyperreality

According to the definition by as defined by the French poststructuralist theorist Jean Baudrillard, in his work *Simulation and Simulacra* (1981), *hyperreal* is “the meticulous reduplication of the real, preferably through another reproductive medium, such as photography” (Habib, 2014, p 347). The term hyperreality is used to understand the situations in four possibly different occasions that one undergoes experience.

First, it is more than one reality. For example, sometimes in our dreams during sleep, we are aware of the fact we are dreaming. In these lucid dreams, we have the awareness of that the reality around us is just a dream and we

know that we are “in fact” just sleeping. We have that conscious awareness regarding that difference between a dream and a reality. The dream reality (where we fly, run at the speed of light, etc.) is one reality and physical reality (where we sleep in our bed) is another reality and the mind is aware of them both. This awareness brings the experience of hyperreality. (Yurt, 2022, pp. 817-188)

From this comprehension, Baudrillard opined that the hyperreality is “the generation by models of a real without origin or reality” (189). It stands for the substitute without the original in which a situation is presented where the mind is unable to differentiate between a reality and as stimulation of reality. “It is when the mind is aware of two different realities but can’t quite figure out where one ends and other one begins. In Baudrillard, this sense of hyperreality is directly related to his understanding of semiotics. The hyperreal is what’s left when both the signified and signifier (of a sign) disappeared, when there’s no more connection between a referent and a reference”. (189)

Drawing all strings of accord from the description, one can identify how the hyperreality is relevant in *When The River Sleeps*. Right from the get-go (even the first chapter, titled *Waking Dreams*, itself), the hyperreality is set in an instant.

Vilie plunged his hand into the river, it was cold – close to freezing – and perfectly still. It was just the way it should be. The river had gone to sleep. Everything was as the seer had told him. Almost imperceptibly, he slid forward and entered the water and plucked a smooth stone from the bottom of the river. In a similar motion, he pulled his arm out of the water and stood still. But it was too late. He felt through the soles of his feet that a great force had awakened. Before he could reach the shore, the water had swelled above his waist – the river had come alive! In an instant, the great torrents had tethered his legs in its twisting undercurrents, dragging him down forcibly into its depths. Vilie’s struggles were feeble against the force

of rushing watering... he flung out his hand and it hit the edge of the bed. It then dawned on him that he had been dreaming again. (Kire pp. 01-02)

It is interesting to take note on how the title itself gives off the essence of hyperreality where the author ingeniously interweaves two contrasting connotations to produce a brilliant vehicle of where the novel will take the readers to. Sarma, in a Raiot book review of the novel (2016) remarks, “the goal of a great novel is to uplift itself from its immediate reality and become universal. It’s an enormous task and you cannot achieve it by ignoring the immediate reality.” This stands unquestioned because the novel goes beyond the edge of human existence and to where the cost of the journey is wisdom.

In the context of the novel, the elements of hyperreality are overflowing in every pages. “The emergence of magic in literary works is a long historical journey of human thought. When everything is taken for granted, magic related to super power more than human’s reach... Magic reforms from supernatural power into hyperpower of technologies as the product of hyper-rationality and becomes hyperreality” (Pujiati 03). Eternal treasured canons of hyperreality texts such as *One Hundred Years of Solitude* by Gabriel Garcia Marquez in which one is drawn to how the author takes into account aspects of life that is inclined to be neglected by written history, involving inexpiable genocide, superstition, stereotypes and the exaggeration of feelings. “We are enamoured with Macondo because Gabriel Garcia Marquez places it within a definite space and time” (Sarma, 2016, pp. 01). Kire is able to employ the same effect in her forest. She does not necessarily forgo the reality but it is just not her point of epicentre. “The Nagas strongly believe in the connection between man and animals since the time of lore and even to this day, there are people who possess different animal spirit”. (Tialila, 2022, p. 201)

The hyperreality in the novel is heightened in chapter twenty. A very faint line is drawn between the reality and the stimulation of reality in this chapter titled *Forest Etiquette* where Vilie enters the stimulation realm as he falls asleep;

He was being chased by angry spirits that were about to catch up with him. But he was paralysed by cramps in his calves that prevented him from taking even one step further. The leader of the spirits was a hair-covered old man who was in a terrible rage. Cursing and spitting, he jumped on Vilie's back and began to pull out his hair. The pain made Vilie cry out. He saw that the other spirits were closing in on him and he was terrified of what horrific death they would visit upon him. Presently he woke with a start, and relief washed over him as he realised it was only a dream. (Kire, 2014, p. 82)

Baudrillard's observation of the contemporary world as a simulacrum where the reality has been replaced by false images is illustrated in the above lines. However, it must be distinguished that there is a fine line between magic realism and the understanding of hyperreality.

Magical realist simulacra do not share the shallowness of Baudrillard's hyperreality – a world in which the distinctions between signified and signifier have all but disappeared through successive reproductions of previous reproductions of reality; the magical realist image stands apart, first because it is the result of an aporetic attitude toward reality, and second because it recreates the real – the limit events that resists representation – as an immediate, *felt* reality. (Arva, 2008, p. 60)

This is what is unique in Kire's *When The River Sleeps*, because she is able to deliver an essential fable in the absence of embellishments and relates the events in a rather pragmatic tone. "Critics would call it magic realism, but this is more akin to a conjures up the fantastic without explanation and we implicitly trust the telling". (Sarma, 2016, p. 01)

The essence of hyperreality it seen to be at its pinnacle point between the end of chapter twenty-four and the chapter twenty-five at full length. As Vilie and Kani set foot in the territory of the sleeping river to facing the spirit widow-women who guarded the river. Kire writes, "they chanted as they walked back – a haunting little

chant that Vilie thought he had heard before. Not in his waking moments, but in dreams and shadow moments between waking and dreaming” (Kire, 2014, p. 101). A little further, “there was something so forbidding about them; both in the chanting that so strongly resembled funeral chants and in the stern way they held themselves as they walked in file back to wherever they had their bleak lodgings” (101-102).

For Baudrillard, the transformation from the real to the hyperreal takes place when the representation gives a way to the stimulation. He explains, “the unreal is no longer that of dream or of fantasy, of a beyond or a within, it is that of a *hallucinatory resemblance of the real with itself*” (Simulations 142). This reference of hyperreality can be discerned in the novel through and through as to the blend of superstitious beliefs and the objectivity is a representation that accommodates the stimulation in the novel.

Interrogating Animism

The theory of Animism can be found to be relevant in the novel, which is often overlooked while putting the focus on the aspects magical realism, hyperreality and ecological element. As defined by Edward Burnett Taylor in his distinguished book *Primitive Culture* (1871), “Animism characterizes tribes very low in the scale of humanity, and thence ascends, deeply modified in its transmission, but from first to last preserving an unbroken continuity, into the midst of high modern culture” and also opined, “I propose her, under the name of Animism, to investigate the deep-lying doctrine of Spiritual Brings, which embodies the very essence of Spiritualistic views” or “the general belief in spiritual beings”. In the terms of Taylor, the belief can intervene in the lives of human beings and in the natural world and is claimed to be historically the earliest form of religion or religious belief. His definition of animism “thus includes a belief in souls, in controlling deities and a hierarchy of subordinate spirits”. (Bishop, 2022, p. 01)

By understanding how Animism is the idea that “all things – animate or inanimate – possess a spirit or an essence” (Perkins, 2019, p. 01), it is a hallmark in many ancient religions, for the most part, the indigenous tribal cultures. “Animism is a foundational element in the development of ancient human spirituality, and it can be identified in different forms throughout major modern world religions” (01). As an anthropological construct, the term is used to determine similar threads of spirituality between contrasting systems of beliefs. It is however, not considered to be a religion in its own right, but rather an attribute of different practices and beliefs.

Recognized by world’s major organized religions, from the example of Shinto, the traditional religion of Japan which is known to be practiced by more than 112 million people. “Ancient Shinto was polytheistic. People found *kami* in nature, which ruled seas or mountains, as well as in outstanding men. They also believed in *kami* of ideas such as growth, creation, and judgement”. (Studocu, 2021-2022, p. 04)

From the comprehension of the development of animism through Souls, Phantoms and Dreams, E. B. Tylor proposed to explain the ideas within the primitive peoples at the lower cultural level.

First he observed two phenomena of interest to the primitive cultures. The first concerned what makes the difference between a living body and a dead one, and what causes waking, sleep, trance, disease, and death. The second concerned those human shapes that appeared in dreams and visions. In terms of **dreams**, Taylor states that the human beings experience their dreams in that they really feel like they are moving on a spiritual space where bodies are not needed. In a dream, one can observe other things happening, fly, pass through walls, engage in battle, all of which feel very real. According to Taylor, many primitive cultures interpreted dreams as being real experiences of things actually happening and it is perhaps because of this that the so-called “savage philosopher” inferred that every person has two things belonging to him: a **life** and a **phantom**. (Bishop, 2022, p. 01)

This pattern of dreaming and the realistic feeling of it consistently reoccurs with Vilie in *When The River Sleeps*. The marvel that the readers are rendered is redundant through the parable. The animistic element that is interwoven with the ‘heart stone’ is colossal in a way that Vilie’s zeal to catch the ‘stone’ ‘when the river is sleeping’ becomes a “manifestation of our inner seeker. Through him we traverse various universes to come to the point of finality” (Satapathy, 2020, p. 01). In this regard, Taylor’s noteworthy line from *Primitive Culture* (2016):

The notion of a ghost-soul animating man while in the body, and peering in dream and vision out of the body, is found deeply ingrained... the primitive animistic doctrine is thoroughly at home among savages. (Taylor, 2016, p. 09)

Thus, can sustain the idea of animism that is relevant in the novel.

Conclusion

The acquiring of indigenous knowledge occurs from the world that is immediate to the individual and its tribal experiences. “Indigenous people gather their knowledge through observation of their physical world. They learn and get experience from the forest ecology around them as well as the world of spirit” (Mandal, 2019, p. 1376). However, obstacles and challenges with the coming of modernization appeared in the horizon, compelling writers from the indigenous communities to attempt to recoup the authenticity and roots of their cultures and narratives.

Through this, the importance and the significance of oral narratives came into the frame of indigenous writers, which became the primary tool to represent the cultures of their communities.

Easterine Kire, known to be “the first Naga writer in English” who “has dipped her quill amply into the rich Naga folk traditions” (Balantrapu, 2015, p. 01), in her book *When the River Sleeps*, there are multiple resonances of the traditional story telling technique which sets the bar on the other indigenous novella. All in all, it “show an inherent stability to counteract the violent and rather uncertain present that Kire

finds in the oral tradition (legend and myths) of Nagaland” (Bhargava, 2019, p. 104). It is further argued that for Kire, “Nagaland becomes a space juxtaposing several spaces – a space marred by conflict along with a tapestry where myth, legends, stories conglomerate with lived realities of a people” (104). In an interview, Kire commented, “We felt we needed to create written Naga Literature. We have so much oral narratives but with oral dying out, it’s all going to be lost.”

From the discussion, it can be seen as to how Kire, throughout her novel, justifies her duty as an artist to be the spokesperson of the Naga life and culture. There is a fetching connection between the psyche, which is represented by the river, and heart, represented by the heart-stone, in order to bring out the true side and characters of Vilie, which is again a representative of the goodness of the Naga people.

“He (Vilie) is born in a supernatural and mystic community which is based on animism. The death of his beloved makes him leave his family and his desire for the heart-stone leads him to the revelation, an expedition that unravels the Naga culture through a confrontation with the mystic and supernatural world”. (Mandal, 2019, p. 1386)

As Tilottima Mishra puts, “the scribal tradition is a recent one amongst the Nagas and before the development of a script for the Naga languages through the efforts of the American Baptist missionaries, literature was confined only to the oral form.”

In light of this, romantic ecology and hyperreality compliments the indigenous epistemology and the aesthetics that Kire penetrates her vision “into the intricacies of Naga life and phenomenal observations stir the mind of the readers in a such a way that they indulge in automatic introspection” (Bhattacharya, 2020, p. 757). It is without a question that she delivers the fundamentals and requisites of indigenous knowledge as a vehicle to corroborate the resilience of the human race. In her speech at the International Congress of PEN in Norway, Kire states that, “the telling of a story is a spiritual exercise that is an integral part of the healing of a people’s psychological wounds...Naga literature is facing a dismissive neo-colonial

attitude.”

Thus, it is noted that, “Kire’s novel serve as a crusade to being about a radical transformation in the perception of the mainstream society towards Naga Indigeneity” (Bhattacharya, 2020, p. 757). *When The River Sleeps* is therefore a celebration of the Naga Epistemology through oral narrative and its indigenous aesthetics analysed from the light of Romantic Ecology and Hyperreality. Paul Pimomo rightfully comments, “Easterine Kire is the keeper of her people’s memory, their griot. She is a master of the unadorned language that moves because of the power of its evocative simplicity.”

Putting it into a historical sense, the moral philosophy of indigenous epistemology and aesthetics in India are consolidated in the collective of aboriginal peoples. It is the politics of instinctive behaviour that protects oneself from harm, subsequently in its own notion of validity. Therefore, *When The River Sleeps* can possibly be interpreted as a local of the universal enigma of the perpetual underyoke of indigenous knowledge.

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Re-mything Water-life and Rejuvenating Women/ Nature: An Ecofeminist reading of Sarah Joseph's Gift in Green

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Abstract

Discussions on nature, ecosystem and its sustainable development have taken a centre-stage amongst academicians and scientists. Sarah Joseph's novel *Gift in Green* articulates such a vibrant concern in an unparalleled way. The novel talks of a pristine land named Aathi ("beginning" in Malayalam) on an island Valanthakad in Eranakulam district of Kerala and its inhabitants. The paper focuses on how the project of modernity intruded into the serene lives of the village called Aathi and how it marked the beginning of an end ("anthyam" in Malayalam) of the village itself. The island with its typical regional topography had its own mythical tales and folk narratives which spoke of its local culture. It clearly portrays how the commercial culture marginalised the lives of the indigenous people, who are often considered subalterns. The novel tells the saga of their resistance on the preservation of harmonious coexistence between man and nature which had been a part of their lives. The novel *Gift in Green* is a celebration of the rustic life in this island, and it mirrors the rejuvenation of women and nature through the lens of Ecofeminism as propounded by Karren J Warren in *Ecofeminist Philosophy* (2000), Susan Griffin in *Woman and Nature: The Roaring Inside Her* (1979), and Vandhana Shiva in *Ecofeminism* (1993).

Keywords: Ecofeminism, water-life, resilience, postmodern pastorals, conversations, Folk tales, survival, rejuvenation.

Introduction

Writings on nature have always embodied a large corpus of global literature. It has got multiple meanings, ramifications and representations in literature crisscrossing the ages and the cultures. However, having Ecofeminism and ecocritical studies at the helm of the literary and academic circles, has brought a paradigm shift in the conceptual frameworks and ideologies regarding nature writings. Ecocriticism imparted the message of living harmoniously with the denizens of the world, both human and non-human whereas Ecofeminism perfectly blended the domains of nature and women. According to Karren J Warren (2000) the meaning of “ecofeminism” can be extended in such a way that “...trees, water, food production, toxins, animals and more generally naturism(the unjustified domination of nonhuman nature) are feminist issues because understanding them helps one understand the interconnections among the dominations of women and other subordinated groups of human (other human others), on the one hand and the domination of non-human nature, on the other hand” (pp.1-2).

With its advent of ecofeminism as a literary trend, numerous writers have addressed the relations between man and nature in general and the symbiotic relationship between women and nature in particular. Ecofeminism brings together elements of both feminist and Green movement, while at the same time offering a challenge to both. Françoise d’Eaubonne, a French feminist coined the term ‘Ecofeminism’ which reiterates that both women and nature are devastated by the patriarchal society. Economists formerly struggle against the desolation of nature and furnish awareness about inequitable state of woman and nature due to the dominance of male - centered society. The man treats both nature and woman as objects or “others”. Besides the exploitation of nature and gender discrimination, it also deals with the spiritual connection between woman and nature.

One of the central tenets of ecofeminism is that the personal problem that women face and the degradation of the natural world must be seen in the context

of a social - political culture, as personal is political, that denigrates both women and nature and subordinates feminine consciousness in favour of a masculine value -system based on fear and subjugation. Rosemary Reuther, a pioneering figure in ecofeminism and a theologian, urged women and environmentalists to stand together to end patriarchal systems that privilege hierarchies, and to control unequal socio-economic relations. Ecofeminism emerged as a literary discipline to unravel the interconnections and to define the web of relationships that exist within the patriarchal system. From the beginnings of human history, men treated nature as a source of the income while women treated nature as a resource for their livelihood. Any upheavals or disturbances in nature can affect their lives adversely, like deforestation or landslides or drought, all having a negative impact upon their lives and families. Bina Agrawal (2012) by highlighting the attachment of women with nature asserts:

An example of female prominence in the defense of natural forests comes from India in 1906. As forest clearing was expanding conflict between loggers and government and peasant communities increased. To thwart resistance to the forest clearing, the men were diverted from their villages to a fictional payment compensation site and loggers were sent to the forests. The women left in the villages; however, protested by physically hugging themselves to the trees to prevent their being cut down, giving rise to what is now called the Chipko movement, an environmentalist movement initiated by these Indian women (which also is where the term tree-huggers originated). This conflict started because men wanted to cut the trees to use them for industrial purposes while women wanted to keep them since it was their food resource and deforestation was a survival matter for local people. (p. 51)

From its inception, ecofeminism foregrounded the idea that women are either biologically or metaphorically closer to nature. The closeness or proximity to nature have got ample representations in literature and with the advent of postmodernism, the ideologies have been deconstructed, to an extent to show that how patriarchal

structure is responsible for the twin dominations of women and nature. Nowadays, ecofeminism focuses in the process of re-visioning human relationships with the natural world by consciousness- raising on the possible stories and myths related to the landscape and natural elements. It tended to be more inclusive, to foreground the areas that had been ignored so far from nature writing. As Gretchen T Legler (1997), an ecofeminist writer, asserts, “most of the contemporary women writers have evolved a new mode of writing, “postmodern pastoral”- “ a posthumanist construction of human relationships with nature that makes more sense in a postmodern world, a vision that is informed by ecological and feminist theories, and one that imagines human/nature relationships as “conversations” between knowing subjects” (p.229). In postmodern pastoral narratives, nature is not a separate entity or an “other”, but it a co-existing entity along with humans. Nature is represented as an active embodied subject intervening on the lives of the inhabitants incessantly. The present paper focuses on how Sarah Joseph presented nature as an active embodied subject in *Gift in Green* and how she articulated the re- mything of water life through the rejuvenation of women and nature in Aathi (the name of the village in the novel).

Sara Joseph is one of the most prominent contemporary women writers from Kerala who carved out a space in global literature with her evocative moving stories. An amazing story teller with meticulous observation of the world around her, a spokesperson for the voiceless, and an agile environmental activist who filled her stories full of life and its subtle nuances. Her collection of short stories ‘Paapathara’ is considered a milestone to feminist writing in Malayalam. Her works are essentially liberalistic and convey the trials and tribulations of various oppressed groups. The novel *Othappu: The scent of the Other Side* is about women’s earning for a true understanding of spirituality and her own sexuality. *Oorukaaval* and *Alohari Anantham* are the other novels written by her. The struggles of women in the dominant social, cultural and economic structures are the major theme of her novels. Her novel *Aalabayude Penmakkal*(*Daughter of God, The Father*) bagged both the prestigious

Kendra Sahitya Akademi Award and Vayalar Award. She is the founder of 'Manushi', an organization of thinking women. She is now seen more as a public intellectual who voices the concerns of women who are silenced by hegemonic forces. She is resolute in her opposition to all structures and institutions that formalise power, be that of the family or the church.

The fictional world of Sarah Joseph is a panorama where she portrays woman in her discriminative and self-conscious phases. Her stories offer a blue print of individual woman's specific reactions to the power relations operative in society. In her stories like "Inside Every Woman Writer" there are the epiphanies of womanhood. There is a complex yet fantastic symbolism for each story which makes it radiantly different from other women's writing. The stories of Sarah Joseph have a splash of magic realism which at one time illuminates the reader and on the other hand transforms the inner landscape of the reader.

Simultaneously published in English and Malayalam, *Gift in Green* is an unconventional, yet mystical novel about the relationship between a land and its inhabitants. Settled in an unravished and unravaged Village named Aathi, the novel exposed a pristine world full of natural beauty and purity. Sarah Joseph (2011) described the village as, "in Aathi, the air was light, the water pristine and the wind pure" (61). It is somewhat like a lagoon, it lies-cool and serene- in the womb of an inviolate purity. It acts as a counter space against all kinds of material and political invasions and exploitations. The village resembled an exceptionally beautiful island called Valanthakkadu in Ernakulam district of Kerala. About fifty families who are wholly depending on fishing, picking mussels and farming Pokkali rice constitute the inhabitants of this island. They were happy about this lot and this same ideology of complacency and contentment could be seen in Aathi and among its inhabitants. *Gift in Green* evokes a symbiotic relationship that exists between the land and its people. But with the coming of Kumaran, who once left his homeland and abandoned the water-life, with the modernity and exposure of the big city, the doomsday (*anthyam* in Malayalam) began for Aathi (means beginning in English). He introduced modernity

and modern resources in Aathi- planned to build a new bridge, a new golden temple in the place of the shrine of the Thampuran, and all possible means to market the resources of the land. It caused a conflict among the inhabitants. Komban Joy, Prakashan and Ambu took the sides of Kumaran and characters like the storyteller Noor Muhammad, poet Markose, Dinakaran, Ponmani, Karthiyani and Kunjimathu defended the land from all kinds of exploitations. The plot revolves around the decay, death and phoenix like regeneration of Aathi along with its people. *Gift in Green* tells the tale of the resilience of the village Aathi, the protagonist of the novel, in strong ecofeminist terms. Sarah Joseph articulated the ideologies of ecofeminism through “the women of Aathi” to present the atrocities done to nature along with those to women. With the introduction of the commercial culture Kumaran tried to break the harmony and biodiversity of the land. When the covenant between the water and the life of the people breaks down, nature emerges as a fiery power in the form of a flood and it revived everything “naturally”. As Glen A Love (1996) puts it, ecofeminism forces us to “redirect human consciousness to full considerations of its place in a threatened natural world” (p. 237). Ecofeminism rejects anthropocentrism and androcentrism and instead advocates an integrated sustainable culture which holds the cosmos as a whole. Its biopolitics stands for a wholesome way of life- there is no discontinuity between human beings and nature and all life forms should be treated equally. That’s what *Gift in Green* communes with the world.

Water-life and Myth of Aathi

The description and myth of the land with its people who firmly believed that “if there is water, we can survive” (Joseph, 2011, p.45) is inextricably connected with water-life . As our earlier civilizations took their birth on riversides, Aathi too had its origin amidst water. Life seemed them to be like a deep, bottomless lagoon. It was water encircled them as the un-ending, ever-renewing fountain spring of life. People began their life there, a land untouched by human hand and utterly unknown to others. In the sludge and soil they toiled to grow paddy and cultivated pokkali rice

and mitigated their hunger and the hunger of the future generations. As women are the reservoirs of stories all around, in Aathi women continued to narrate the history and myth of Aathi to their children. A description on the primeval purity of Aathi cannot be completed without a narration on the Greenbangle- the mangrove forest in Aathi, as

it encircled Aathi, an enchanting world in itself, its waters cool and serene. Sitting in that rare world of impregnable silence, immune to the noise of men and machines, Noor Muhammad would listen intently to the subtle voices of the cosmos and enjoy their variety and the soothing sweetness of their harmony. Watching the fallow leaves fall noiselessly on the water, then float towards and accumulate at the bank, he would weave the tapestry of his life interpretations. He would listen to the blossoming of flowers, watch the moss dance, the glow-worms emerge from their hideouts and read the trails of tiny worms. His mind would clear, his lungs full with a new vitality and his stomach with heavenly happiness. 'Rejoice, O my heart', he would tell himself. (Joseph, 2011, p.25)

To be with nature was the primary source of rejoicing for the people. From this description, it is clear that Aathi was both a pristine idyllic place and an abode of peaceful community that nourished and protected all forms of life celebrating its diversity. That is viewed in the peaceful co-existence of different animal species. The land of Aathi had formed the natural habitats for different animal species and plants. Kumaran breaks the green bangle, the virgin forest by burning it simply for his personal life. His actions brought havoc upon the land, changed the integrity of the society that had previously moulded their lives in preserving the natural resources where they started selling their lands to him. He had become the corporate landlord, an aspect that gave him a chance to exploit the naturally existing resources for economic gains.

Nature-Women Coexistence in *Gift in Green*

It is really imperative to know how the life in Aathi especially that of women are closely tied to water. Water is the source of their livelihood. No one in Aathi can defy the water-life and the myths related to it. As the storyteller Noor Muhammad says, "...but, all stories, irrespective of their location, exist in the womb of water. There is water inside and outside stories of every kind. Stories enfold the hope for water where there is no water" (Joseph, 2011, p.148). Water promises life and survival for them and ever since there was a rupture in this, Aathi has lost its integrity and it has been "spreading beyond its boundaries" (p.153) with the modernisation introduced by Kumaran. There is an account of a village called Meenwari in the novel. It is so unique as only women used to catch fish in that region. Sarah Joseph says, "after supper, carrying their pots, vattaras and nets, they would reach Meenwari, walking and swimming and claim the night for themselves. It was they who named this place Meenwari" (p.149). When nature is at risk, it was the women folk who identifies it first. They scrutinised the changes that happened over the water and the high tides and the fear that Aathi was in peril of being ruined haunted each and every woman, especially Kunjimathu and Shailaja at the lead. "Life in Aathi had begun to lose its serenity because of the continual incursions from the external world. Not only human beings but also animals, birds and fishes were being affected" (Joseph, 2011, p.151).

Kunjimathu, jilted by Kumaran, was truly symbolic of how men exploit female body just as he exploits nature. Sarah Joseph drew an analogy between women and nature as ecofeminism throws light upon how female body can be treated as a territory subdued by the patriarchy. As Vandhana Shiva states in *Ecofeminism* (1993), "Colonization of seed, reflects the patterns of colonization of women's bodies. Profits and power become intimately linked to invasion into all biological organisms" (p.29). Similarly Kayal (the name itself resonates water), the young girl reaches Aathi who was severely exploited by the patriarchal society. Gitanjali, her

mother, took the child to Aathi upon the instructions of her Guru. The possible panacea for Kayal's malady is Nature itself, as the Guru prescribed "Know the water", that's it. "Let Kayal know the water...Not know in the usual sense of the term. We must know the water as the lotus knows it: rooted in the sludge below, growing its stem in the water, unfurling its leaves on the surface of the water and offering its wet and watery face to the sun" (Joseph, 2011, p.61). The healing power of the nature was sung by Markose the poet:

Morning breeze, water beds,
 Birds and trees,
 Dazzling dewdrops...
 Pour a drop of this peace
 Into the burning mind
 Of that ravaged child. (Joseph, 2011, p.61)

***Gift in Green* as a Postmodern Pastoral narrative**

The vigour of water in *Gift in Green* was exquisitely portrayed when Kunjimathu listened to the screams of the water under the granite embankment. She could listen to the suffocation of water and its frustrations. The most powerful character that Sarah Joseph delineates in the novel is Water itself. Its serenity, chillness, beauty, power and fury was there. When men brought a discordance with nature, his dark future is revealed through the prophetic vision of Kunjimathu and it would be like this:

Visions, one after the other, flashed before Kunjimathu's eyes.
 Paddy fields, parched.
 Trees, dry and withered.
 The earth, cracked.
 Wells, dried up.
 Cattle, tormented by thirst.
 Birds, perishing.

Children, howling in hunger...
Desert storms raging with a vengeance.
The burning sand it brought along, covering the land,
Red-hot rocks.
Thorny bushes.
Scorching heat.
Freezing cold.
A woman who wandered about, aflame within and without, in the wilderness.
Kunjimathu. (Joseph, 2011, pp.196-197)

Here, Kunjimathu and nature became one, a single entity. Nature could be seen as an active, embodying subject here. The mutual conversations between Kunjimathu and water kindled fire among the women and how the women of Aathi took firm decisions to defend and protect their own land is the most engrossing scene of the novel itself. How the women built a bund so as to save water is clearly pictured here. "The band of mothers"(334) clubbed together in unison, took a decision to protect the nature by any means without even consulting the male folks, minds that were smouldering with grief over the plight of their land and their children.

Susan Griffin in her book *Woman and nature: the Roaring Inside her* developed the idea that women are innately closer to the natural world. In the prologue to the book she wrote: "He says that woman speaks with nature. That she hears voices from under the earth. That wind blows in her ears and trees whisper to her. That the dead sing through her mouth and the cries of the infants are dear to her. But for him the dialogue is over. He says he is not part of the world, that he was set on this world as a stranger. He sets himself apart from woman and nature" (p.1).

Celebration of Folk life

The story telling nights and the exclusive rituals associated with it were a part of Aathi's culture. Seven stories have been narrated in the novel which reaffirms the sovereignty and sanctity of water-life. These stories owed to an assortment of resources such as the Holy Bible, the holy Quran, Zen and Sufi traditions, the

Puranas, folk narratives, historical events and those attributed to the life of St. Francis of Assisi. These stories have been recreated and reinterpreted within the alchemy of Aathi. What is unique in the narration is that all these seven stories were centered on water and how did water sustain human life across the ages. The author uses the analogies found in nature to show how the inner human landscape and island topography are related. The novel's premise, which is the decay of society, is vividly illustrated by the natural imagery of water. In the end, the surge of the flood successfully conveys the ability of nature to purify itself. Throughout the entire book, the effects of mindless progress and the battle between culture and nature are apparent. The novel paints the intense agony of a community and men's audacity to nature through the lens of Ecofeminism.

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Tribal Research & Cultural Institute

The Tribal Research & Cultural Institute was established in the year 1970 under the Tribal Welfare Department with following broad objectives :

- To conduct different research studies like development of language & culture, socioeconomic condition of Tripura tribes, collection of historical elements and evaluation studies.
- To assist research scholars in the conduct of research works related to the tribes of Tripura.
- To promote Tribal culture like tribal folk song, folk dance, folk music through Tripura State Academy of Tribal Culture affiliated to Tripura University (A Central University).
- To demonstrate tribal heritage, culture, socio-economic condition, dresses, ornament and every day life through a State Tribal Museum.
- To document Socio-economic & traditional aspects of Tripura tribes through production of films and establishment of a rich Social Science Library.
- To organise State & National Level Seminar on Tribal life & Culture and Languages.
- To publish books related to Socio-economic condition on Tribal life & culture of the State and reprints the rare and old books related to Tripura.

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